

Enhancing Sustainable Employment in Iriga City: A Framework for Action

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Abstract

The lack of framework for Iriga City PESO posed apprehension towards its services. This research evaluated the office's performance via the jobseekers' and enterprise employers' perceived effectiveness focusing on the four dimensions of performance management: accessibility, outcomes achieved, satisfaction with services, and efficiency of services. Convergent parallel design was utilized in this study in which the quantitative and qualitative data were analyzed separately first before integrating them together. The 4-point Likert scale targeting the jobseekers and enterprise employers in the city provided the quantitative data, while structured interviews collect qualitative perspectives. The findings revealed that from the jobseekers' point of view, the services of the office is moderately accessible ($M = 2.67$), with substantial outcomes achieved ($M = 2.77$). They were also highly satisfied ($M = 2.74$) with the services and rated the office with established efficiency ($M=2.73$). The enterprise employers also think the same way ($M_{accessibility} = 2.70$, $M_{outcomes} = 2.64$,

$M_{satisfaction} = 2.66$, and $M_{efficiency} = 2.73$). The results also showed that there is no significant difference between the jobseekers' and enterprise employers' perceptions, with p-values: accessibility: 0.72, outcomes achieved: 0.14, satisfaction with services: 0.31, and efficiency of services: 0.99. These results, as well as the findings from the thematic analysis of the qualitative data, were incorporated to the Sustainable Framework for Action (SFA). The inputs of the framework are: database system, human capital training, and operational resources. From there, the expected outputs are: operational efficiency, matching quality, and extensive programming. The outcomes are: candidate tracking, employability enhancement, and inclusivity and access. All of these result to the impact which is sustainable employment in the city. By refining the services of Iriga City PESO through this framework, they can provide better services to the jobseekers and employers alike, promoting a robust employment landscape in Iriga City.

Keywords: *performance management; framework; PESO; ILO*

I. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

This research aimed to improve the perceived effectiveness of the Iriga City Public Employment Service Office (PESO) employment services by proposing a Sustainable Framework for Action (SFA) based on the Performance Management element of the International Labour Organization's (ILO) Delivery Framework.

Specifically, it aimed to:

1. Describe the Jobseekers and Enterprise Employers' perceived effectiveness level of performance management of Iriga City PESO's employment services in terms of the four dimensions: Accessibility, Outcomes Achieved, Satisfaction with Services, and Efficiency of Service;

2. Compare the Jobseekers and Enterprise Employers' perceived effectiveness of the Performance Management of Iriga City PESO's employment services in terms Accessibility, Outcomes Achieved, Satisfaction with Services, and Efficiency of Service; and,

3. Propose a Sustainable Framework for Action (SFA) based on the ILO's Performance Management element incorporating the feedback from the Jobseekers and Enterprise Employers.

II. SCOPE and DELIMITATION

This study is a comprehensive evaluation of the employment services provided by the Iriga City PESO focusing of the Performance Management aspect. This also proposed a Sustainable Framework for Action based on the underpinnings of the delivery framework of the ILO. The respondents are the 2024 jobseekers in Iriga City and enterprise employers duly registered within the city. The course of this study ran from January to December 2025. This study only focused on the perceived effectiveness of the jobseekers and enterprise employers about the four of the Performance Management elements of the ILO namely, Accessibility, Outcomes Achieved, Satisfaction with Services, and Efficiency of Service. This study employed a mixed method of research specifically the convergent parallel design method.

The other elements of the delivery framework provided by ILO are not part of the focus of this study since the employment office already satisfied them based on their annual accomplishment report. To avoid observational bias in the perceived effectiveness of the operations of Iriga City PESO, its employees were not selected as the target population of this study. The impact of the proposed SFA is not evaluated in this study due to the limited time frame as well as the lack of legal basis that compels the employment office to religiously follow the proposed SFA.

III. THEORETICAL/CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The theory that was used as an anchor of this study is Public Value Theory coined by Mark Moore in the year 1999. It is largely used by government agencies to improve their productivity and effectiveness by creating what so called as public value. This theory puts emphasis on the critical role of public managers or leaders in improving their effectiveness by making a positive perception of the services they offer to the public. Furthermore, the public managers or leaders should provide products or services that results to the satisfaction of the customer (Moore, 1999).

In the context of this study, the public managers equate to the employment office in focus — the Iriga City PESO, while the customers include both the jobseekers and enterprise employers. Based on the theory, a significant improvement in the success of the services offered by Iriga City PESO can be obtained by making a positive perceived effectiveness by the jobseekers and enterprise employers. That is the premise that this study offers. In order to make an impactful framework, the opinions, perceptions, and firsthand experiences of the jobseekers and enterprise employers must be taken into account. This is also in congruence with the delivery framework of the ILO since it also focuses on the aforementioned target population.

Another theory that supported this study is the New Public Management Theory laid out by Christopher Hood on 1991. This theory is a conglomeration of the practices from the business industry into the public sector. By adopting systems from the business industry as well as performance management strategies, the public sector’s operations and services become more efficient and effective (Hood, 1991).

This theory acts as a scaffold in this study since a framework that is largely used in the business sector, the Performance Management Framework of the International Labour Organization, was used as a guide in creating a framework for a government office, which is the Iriga City Public Employment Service Office. It only goes to show that adopting practices from one sector to be implemented in another is not a new practice. Modifications as well as contextualization are necessary, however, in order to ensure that the main goal are still upheld. In the case of this study, data gathered from the office’s main customers will be used to make sure that the framework directly addresses the concerns of PESO.

Figure 1 shows the theoretical framework. In it, the data that were collected in this study i.e., the perceived effectiveness of Iriga City PESO’s services in the four dimensions of the performance management was analyzed through the lens of the Public Value Theory. The input were used as a basis for creating the proposed Sustainable Framework for Action for the employment office. Moreover, the incorporation of practices from the business sector into the public operations is supported by the New Public Management Theory. This study used the Performance Management Framework of the International Labour Organization as the basis for the proposed framework for Iriga City PESO.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

In creating the SFA for the operations of Iriga City PESO, figure 2 shows the conceptual paradigm using the Input-Process-Output (IPO) Model.

The input for this study includes the PPAs of the Iriga City PESO for the calendar year 2024 from the office’s annual accomplishment report. This serves as the baseline data regarding the performance of

the Iriga City PESO. The other input for this study is the perceived effectiveness of the jobseekers and enterprise employers regarding the four dimensions: Accessibility, Outcomes Achieved, Satisfaction with Services, and Efficiency of Service, under the Performance Management Element of the delivery framework of ILO. This serves as a guide in drafting the SFA that was proposed to Iriga City PESO.

The process for this study starts with analyzing the data from the annual accomplishment report of Iriga City PESO for the calendar year 2024 through the lens of the delivery framework of ILO. It is followed by the analysis of the data gathered from the perceived effectiveness of the jobseekers and enterprise employers of the four dimensions under the performance management element of the delivery framework of ILO. This was done by getting the mean of the data and identifying whether there is a significant difference between the perceived effectiveness of the services of Iriga City PESO by the jobseekers and the enterprise employers via independent sample t-test. The qualitative data were analyzed via thematic analysis. Lastly, the proposed SFA was drafted considering the analyzed data gathered from the samples.

The output of this study is the proposed Sustainable Framework for Action for improving the performance management of Iriga City PESO. This is endorsed to the employment service office for their own use.

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework

In making the proposed Sustainable Framework for Action, the delivery framework of ILO was used, specifically the third element which is the Performance Management. Figure 3 shows that Performance Measurement Framework (PMF) which was precisely the structural basis for the SFA.

In the framework, the first element introduced was the result itself: the impact. Impact, in this context, is defined as the long-term effect of the proposed framework. In this study, the desired impact is sustainable employment in Iriga City. To achieve the impact, certain elements are needed to be done.

First on the list is the input. It pertains to the types of resources needed in order to achieve the impact. In this study, the focus is the perceived effectiveness of Iriga City PESO from the jobseekers and enterprise employers. Therefore, they were part of the input. Aside from that, the performance of Iriga City PESO in the last year was also used as a baseline data for the SFA.

From the input, outputs can be generated. This relates to the short-term activities or programs that are needed to be conducted at least daily in order to achieve the impact. After the responses from the jobseekers and enterprise employers were gathered, the outputs was proposed.

The last element is the outcome. This is the direct result of the outputs after being conducted or implemented over a certain period of time. In a way, it is a medium-term results that directly affects the desired impact. The outcome of the SFA was derived from the outputs.

Figure 3: Performance Management Framework

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This study aimed to measure and analyze the jobseekers and enterprise employers' perceived effectiveness of the services of Iriga City PESO based on the four dimensions – Accessibility, Outcomes Achieved, Satisfaction with Services, and Efficiency of Service – of the performance management based on the delivery framework by ILO. Moreover, the study aimed to propose a framework for action based on the performance management element of the ILO and incorporating the feedback from jobseekers and enterprise employers.

In order to achieve these goals, a mixed-methods approach was used. The specific research design employed in this study is the convergent parallel design method or commonly called as concurrent triangulation design. This method was used since both quantitative and qualitative data were collected at the same time. This design is best used to obtain a wider, complementary perspectives in achieving the goals of the research (Creswell & Creswell, 2023).

To measure and analyze whether there is a significant difference between the perceived effectiveness of Iriga City PESO's services through the lens of jobseekers and enterprise employers, a four-point Likert scale was utilized. In achieving the third goal, which is to propose a framework using the feedback from the office's main clients, a structured interview was used. After simultaneously gathering the data, they were analyzed separately first with the quantitative data being subjected to the appropriate test statistics and the thematic approach for the qualitative data. The results were then analyzed concurrently to enrich the discussion of the results. Both sets of data were given equal importance to arrive to a comprehensive conclusion.

B. Respondent/Participants of the Study

There are two main target population of this study. The first target population is the jobseekers. These are the applicants of legal age (18 years old) until 40 years old residing in Iriga City who were actively hunting for job last year. The second target population is the enterprise employers. These are duly-registered employers in Iriga City that usually hire more than one employee within the establishment. These diverse population may include small enterprises to medium and large scale enterprises as long as they employ more than one employee.

Sampling Technique

The study employed purposive sampling. The main criteria for the individuals to be a part of the sample of this study is the jobseeker and enterprise employer must have a direct

involvement in Iriga City PESO's services and programs. The sample was also delimited to those who participated in or were directly connected to Iriga City PESO's employment services during the 2024 calendar year, aligning the data collection with the scope and timeframe of the study.

Since purposive sampling is a type of non-probability sampling, the results of this study cannot be used to statistically generalize the perceived effectiveness of the entire population of jobseekers and enterprise employers. However, the main focus of the study is to propose a working framework for the operations of Iriga City PESO. In order to do so, the research demands richness of information from direct clients of the office. The lack of generalizability may be excused if the quality of the framework is excellent enough to serve its intention. This can only be achieved if the criteria discussed were met by the respondents. The study of Palinkas et al., (2015) supports this disclaimer about the use of purposive sampling in mixed-method researches.

Sample Size

Following the criteria established above, a total of 109 jobseekers were surveyed and interviewed. They are the jobseekers who have direct involvement in the operations and services of Iriga City PESO for the year calendar year 2024.

A total of 52 enterprise employers were selected via purposive sampling. Just like jobseekers, these are employers who participated in the services offered by Iriga City PESO.

C. Data Gathering Tools

This section explains the main data gathering tools used in this study. Since the study employed a mixed method of research, it was necessary to obtain both quantitative data and qualitative data. The quantitative data were primarily used to achieve the first two objectives of this study while the qualitative data were used to achieve the last objective of the study.

A large portion of the data needed in this research were gathered using a survey. The researcher decided to use a four-point scale to highly encourage the respondents to take a clear stance, thus avoiding central tendency error. The indicators in the Likert Scale were modifications of the four salient questions of the performance management element of the delivery framework of the ILO. As discussed by Koeltz and Torres (2017), a good performance management is present when the following questions were answered positively. The first question—“Do all clients have fair and equitable access to services?”—addressed the principle of inclusivity, a central pillar of the ILO's Decent Work Agenda. The authors stressed the importance of ensuring that employment services are accessible to all, including marginalized populations such as persons with disabilities, rural residents, and the economically disadvantaged. Applied in the context of Iriga City PESO, this question acted like a guide in analyzing the agency's registration procedures, outreach strategies, communication channels, and geographical reach to evaluate the extent to which services are truly accessible to all Irigueños.

The second guiding question—“Are the desired outcomes being achieved?”—shifted focus from service outputs to long-term impacts. Outcomes such as increased job placement rates, improved job retention, and higher client income levels are critical indicators of success in PES operations. In this study, data were collected on such indicators to determine whether Iriga City PESO's interventions are leading to meaningful and sustained improvements in the lives of jobseekers and employers alike.

The third question— “Are both jobseekers and enterprises satisfied with the services?”—evaluated service quality from the perspectives of primary beneficiaries. Satisfaction is a crucial determinant of service effectiveness and institutional credibility. To this end, the study used client feedback mechanisms, such as satisfaction surveys and follow-up interviews, to gauge perceptions of the relevance, timeliness, and professionalism of the services provided by Iriga City PESO.

The final question— “Are services delivered efficiently?”—examined the cost-effectiveness and resource optimization of service delivery. Efficiency, as conceptualized in the ILO framework, involves maximizing outputs and outcomes relative to available inputs. The study analyzed indicators such as cost per job placement, time-to-hire metrics, and the client-to-staff ratio to identify potential areas for improving operational efficiency without compromising quality.

The four-point Likert Scale used the following response anchors: 1 = Strongly Disagree (SD), 2 = Disagree (D), 3 = Agree (A), and 4 = Strongly Agree (SA).

The qualitative data were gathered via structured interview. Just like the indicators in the Likert scale, the questions for the structured interview were based on the four core questions for a good performance management as discussed by Koeltz and Torres (2017). Each core question/dimension has five sub-questions, all of which intend to allow the respondents to elaborate their answers.

The survey (Likert Scale) and the questions for the structured interview were pre-tested where a representative sample were asked to accomplish. After doing so, the survey and the questions for the structured interview were assessed and validated using the prescribed validation sheet by three experts in the field.

D. Data Gathering Procedure

The aim of the study is to propose a framework for Iriga City PESO focusing on the performance management as an element of the delivery framework of the ILO. The proposed framework incorporates feedback from the office’s main clients: jobseekers and enterprise employers.

Data collection began by laying out the baseline data. A comprehensive review of Iriga City PESO’s 2024 Annual Accomplishment Report was conducted. This provided foundational insights into the scope, priorities, and outcomes of its employment service initiatives, particularly those aimed at promoting sustainable employment. Based on this review, a structured survey questionnaire was designed to quantitatively assess various dimensions of Iriga City PESO’s service delivery, including accessibility, effectiveness, and client satisfaction. This is needed to achieve the last goal of the study.

After the document analysis and in order to resolve the first two objectives of the study, the survey, as well as the questions for the structured interview were drafted and submitted for validation. Three experts of the field were tapped to validate the survey questionnaire using the university’s Research Instrument Validation Form. The validation form encompassed the face, content, criterion, and construct validity. The validators provided feedback that were incorporated in the questionnaire. Following the validation of tools, the target population of jobseekers and enterprise employers were identified. Since the study intends to focus of these clients, purposive sampling was used. A preliminary informal interview was conducted to make sure that they are

qualified to answer the survey. Once ensured that the person is qualified, the survey was handed over and the respondent is given ample amount of time to answer. Following the survey was the structured interview. The respondents were given an option as to the manner of answering the questions. They can either write their answers or they can answer verbally provided that they consent that the conversation would be recorded and transcribed later on.

The primary purpose of the data-gathering procedure is to establish a structured process for collecting data that aligns with the research objectives and questions. It ensures that data is collected consistently and unbiasedly, facilitating the accurate analysis and interpretation of results.

E. Data Analysis Techniques

The study employed both quantitative and qualitative data analysis techniques which ensured a comprehensive and integrative evaluation of Iriga City PESO's employment services.

For the quantitative data collected via the survey, the main statistical tool used to achieve the first research objective is mean. It was used to summarize respondents' ratings and identify general trends in the four dimensions of performance management: accessibility, outcomes achieved, satisfaction with services, and efficiency of services. The mean of the data gathered were assigned their corresponding interpretation which varies depending on the dimension in question. The mean of the numerical scores was first computed, then it was analyzed. Table 1 shows the corresponding interpretations for each dimension.

Before the conduct of the survey and interview, the informed consent of the respondent were obtained via the university's standardized consent form. The purpose of the survey and interview were thoroughly discussed as well as the entire process of the research. The potential risks and benefits of them participating in the study were also disclosed. During the interview, consent is once again obtained. The respondents were asked if they were comfortable and are willing for the conversation to be recorded for transcribing purposes. Respondents who did not give consent to both processes were not forced in any way to give information about the study.

After that, the respondents who consented in participating in the study were assured that confidentiality in treating the data were upheld which is why sensitive information such as name, address, and the likes were not required to be answered in the survey. Each survey was treated with utmost confidentiality to ensure that respondents' identities were protected and that anonymity is a high priority.

Once gathered, all of the data were stored in a secure place to avoid possible leakage. All the data were treated with utmost confidentiality and discretion. Should the respondent decide to withdraw from the study, the information they had given were disposed of properly.

Table 1
Interpretation of 4-point Likert Scale for the four dimensions of performance management

Mean Numerical Score	Response Anchor	Interpretation			
		Accessibility	Outcomes Achieved	Satisfaction with Services	Efficiency of Services
1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Not Accessible	Limited Outcomes Achieved	Low Satisfaction	Developing Efficiency
	Disagree (D)	Minimally Accessible	Partial Outcomes Achieved	Moderate Satisfaction	Emerging Efficiency
2.50 – 3.49	Agree (A)	Moderately Accessible	Substantial Outcomes Achieved	High Satisfaction	Established Efficiency
	Strongly Agree (SA)	Fully Accessible	Full Outcomes Achieved	Exceptional Satisfaction	Exemplary Efficiency

In addition, independent sample t-test (Welch's T-test) was conducted to determine whether a statistically significant difference existed between the perceived effectiveness of Iriga City PESO's employment services provided by the jobseekers and enterprise employers. This tool was used to achieve the second research goal.

Both the mean and independent sample t-test were conducted using Microsoft Excel's Data Analysis Toolkit. This ensures a more convenient and efficient way of calculating the values and avoiding errors.

For the qualitative data, which were gathered through written interviews, the study applied thematic analysis. This method involved the systematic process of coding, categorizing, and interpreting textual data to identify recurring themes, insights, and meanings. Following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase approach to thematic analysis—familiarization with data, generation of initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the report—the study analyzed participants' narratives in relation to the four guiding questions from the ILO's Performance Management Framework. These themes reflected participants' lived experiences, perceptions, and recommendations regarding Iriga City PESO's service delivery.

To ensure credibility of transcribed responses for the interview, the respondents were shown a copy of their answers for validation. Dependability of data was also secured by making sure a comprehensive audit of the entire data gathering was documented and kept safe for transparency purposes. Finally, confirmability was guaranteed by having an independent verifier to review the analysis, minimizing subjectivity in the discussion.

The integration of statistical results and emergent qualitative themes through triangulation strengthened the study's internal validity and offer a holistic understanding of the employment service outcomes. This approach ensures that both numerical trends and contextual stakeholder perspectives are considered in evaluating the performance of Iriga City PESO's programs.

F. Ethical Considerations

This research adhered to the strict ethical guidelines that ensures the protection of participants' rights and well-being. The stipulations and principles of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 were upheld while gathering the data.

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V. RESULTS and DISCUSSION

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Perceived Effectiveness of the Accessibility of Iriga City PESO's Services

Table 2 shows the results of the survey to the jobseekers in their assessment of accessibility dimension of the performance management of Iriga City PESO.

Table 2
Mean score of the perceived effectiveness of Iriga City PESO's services via the jobseekers in terms of accessibility

ACCESSIBILITY	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
Information about PESO Iriga's services (e.g., Job Fair, Mass Hiring, Career Coaching) is easily accessible to me.	2.80	Moderately Accessible
The registration process for PESO Iriga's services is straightforward and inclusive.	2.73	Moderately Accessible
The physical location and facilities of PESO Iriga are accessible to all, including persons with disabilities.	2.73	Moderately Accessible
PESO Iriga's outreach strategies effectively reach diverse jobseekers in Iriga City.	2.64	Moderately Accessible
PESO Iriga provides clear and sufficient information about available job vacancies.	2.42	Minimally Accessible
OVERALL MEAN	2.67	Moderately Accessible

Note:
 1.00 – 1.49 Not Accessible
 1.50 – 2.49 Minimally Accessible
 2.50 – 3.49 Moderately Accessible
 3.50 – 4.00 Fully Accessible

The results showed that the overall performance of Iriga City PESO, in the accessibility dimension, is perceived by the jobseekers as moderately accessible, having obtained a mean score of 2.67. This implied that, although the services are available and the jobseekers can access them to a considerable extent, there are still certain limitations that they find that prevent full access for them. Among the indicators of accessibility, information accessibility garnered the highest mean ($\bar{x} = 2.80$), indicating a unison among the jobseekers that general information including procedures, requirements, and the likes, are easily obtained and understandable. This suggested that Iriga City PESO has been effective in communicating essential information to jobseekers through their mode of information dissemination. However, despite the generally positive perceived effectiveness across the indicators of accessibility, the accessibility of job vacancy information recorded the lowest mean score of 2.42. This means that even if job vacancy is available, it is not consistently or sufficiently accessible in other channels. As a result, jobseekers experiences difficulty in accessing timely and relevant job vacancy details.

Overall, the findings suggested that Iriga City PESO performs reasonably well in the accessibility dimension. In spite of this, there is a notable gap in the accessibility of job vacancy information. Addressing this gap results to an improved employment matching and enhancing the effectiveness of Iriga City PESO's service.

The results may be attributed to the fact that majority of jobseekers use social media as their primary source of information. This is utilized by Iriga City PESO by employing the robust use of their Facebook page as their main platform for information dissemination. While this platform allows for wide reach and ease of information sharing, its effectiveness is largely dependent on stable internet connection. The relatively low score for the accessibility of job vacancy information may therefore be influenced by the generally weak and intermittent internet connection in the city, which can limit the jobseeker's ability to regularly access online postings.

Although the overall mean score indicated that accessibility is perceived as moderately accessible, the findings suggest that there are still significant areas that needs to be improved. To be specific, the quality, consistency and completeness of job vacancy postings appear to be insufficient. Job postings may lack comprehensive details or they may not be updated consistently. This lack of depth and uniformity in information dissemination may reduce the usefulness of the postings and hinder the jobseekers' ability to make informed employment decisions. Consequently, while current information dissemination methods provide basic level of access, enhancing the clarity, completeness, and regularity of job vacancy information, as well as exploring alternative or supplementary offline channels could improve overall accessibility and ensure that the office's services more effectively respond to the needs of jobseekers. These can be supported by statements like:

"The easiest aspect is that I can just browse information about the PESO Iriga's services on its Facebook page while the most difficult one is that they do not respond on my inquiries/messages immediately"

The jobseeker indicated that they find it easy to access Iriga City PESO's service information through its Facebook page due to convenience and familiarity. The channel allowed the jobseekers to quickly browse updates and announcements without visiting the office personally. However, they noted a significant delay in the response of the office. This suggested that limitations in Iriga City PESO's capacity to provide timely online communication. Responsiveness remains a key area for improvement.

Another jobseeker mentioned that:

“Maaaring hindi naabot ng impormasyon ang mga nasa remote areas ng Iriga City kung hindi sila mismo ang pupunta sa tanggapan ng Iriga City PESO”

(It is possible that those living in the remote areas of Iriga City cannot access the information unless they personally go to the office.)

The respondent raised the concern of the jobseekers in the far flung areas of the city wherein, they may face limited access to information due to geographical barriers coupled with weak internet connectivity. As a result, online platforms are not the most reliable sources of information for them.

The results are in congruence with the findings of Robiyandi and Indarto (2025) and Ribeiro et al. (2024), who emphasized that service accessibility significantly increases when technology is effectively integrated into public service delivery. The relatively positive perception of accessibility in the present study is attributed to the Iriga City PESO's use of digital platforms, particularly social media, as key channels for information dissemination. This observation is further supported by the survey conducted by the Congressional Policy and Budget Research Department (2024), which reported that a majority of Filipinos are actively online and commonly use social media to access information, including employment-related updates.

At the same time, the identified limitations in the accessibility of Iriga City PESO services can be explained by the study of Bachita and Bayoneta (2021), which discussed the fundamental nature and constraints of public employment service offices. Their study highlighted that employment offices often face challenges related to resource limitations, operational capacity, and service scope, which may affect the consistency and depth of service delivery. These structural realities help contextualize the observed gaps in accessibility, suggesting that while technological integration enhances reach, institutional and operational factors continue to influence overall service effectiveness.

Based on the result, the accessibility of the services of Iriga City PESO can be improved by providing sustained funding and continuous training for their staff to formally integrate social media management into the office's core operational processes and Citizen's Charter. They should also invest on other forms of information dissemination. While Facebook is effective, there are areas where internet connectivity is intermittent, plus there are jobseekers who are not well-versed with social media.

Table 3 shows the result of the survey to the enterprise employers in their assessment of accessibility dimension of the performance management of Iriga City PESO.

Table 3
 Mean score of the perceived effectiveness of Iriga City PESO's services via the enterprise employers in terms of accessibility

ACCESSIBILITY	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
PESO Iriga provides adequate support for enterprises during recruitment activities like Job Fairs and Mass Hiring.	2.85	Moderately Accessible
The process for posting job vacancies and recruiting through PESO Iriga is straightforward and efficient.	2.81	Moderately Accessible
Information about PESO Iriga's services for employers (e.g., Special Recruitment Activity, Job Fair) is easily accessible to my enterprise.	2.52	Moderately Accessible
PESO Iriga effectively communicates with employers regarding labor market information and available talent.	2.52	Moderately Accessible
PESO Iriga's services cater to the diverse needs of various enterprises in Iriga City.	2.50	Moderately Accessible
OVERALL MEAN	2.70	Moderately Accessible

Note:
 1.00 – 1.49 Not Accessible
 1.50 – 2.49 Minimally Accessible
 2.50 – 3.49 Moderately Accessible
 3.50 – 4.00 Fully Accessible

The overall assessment of Iriga City PESO's performance in terms of accessibility to services by enterprise employers yielded an overall mean of 2.70, which is interpreted as moderately accessible. This indicated that enterprise employers generally perceive the office's services as available and reachable, although access is not yet optimal. The result suggests that while the office is able to provide assistance to employers, there is still room for improvement in ensuring that services are fully accessible across diverse enterprise needs. Key findings show that enterprise employers find it easy to seek support from Iriga City PESO when implementing recruitment programs, particularly in situations that require the hiring of a large number of employees. This reflects the office's effectiveness in coordinating manpower pooling and facilitating recruitment activities. The indicator with the highest mean score supports this, as enterprise employers expressed strong agreement regarding the office's conduct and support during job fairs and mass hiring events. These activities provide structured and efficient avenues for enterprises to meet potential employees, thereby enhancing the overall accessibility of Iriga City PESO's services.

However, the lowest-rated indicator relates to the versatility of Iriga City PESO's services in catering to the diverse employment requirements of enterprises within the city. This suggests that while the office performs well in standard and large-scale recruitment efforts, it may have limited capacity to address specialized, industry-specific, or unique hiring needs. Such limitations may be influenced by resource constraints or the scope of existing programs. Consequently, improving service flexibility and expanding tailored employment support could further enhance the office's accessibility and responsiveness to enterprise employers.

Looking into the specific indicators of accessibility from the perspective of enterprise employers, it can be deduced that the services of Iriga City PESO are moderately accessible. Although the office is generally able to provide recruitment support, the findings indicate a need for improvement in keeping its services aligned with the rapidly changing demands of the labor market, as this indicator received the lowest mean score. This limitation may be attributed to the increasingly dynamic nature of the labor

market, where employer needs and requirements frequently shift due to economic conditions, industry trends, and technological changes.

In particular, the enterprises may require workers on a short-term, seasonal, or project-based basis, resulting in fluctuating and sometimes unpredictable employment needs. The emergence of temporary and disposable employment arrangements during peak seasons, such as holidays, commercial cycles, and the likes further complicates recruitment demands. These conditions require employment offices to be highly adaptive and responsive. As such, the lower rating suggests that while the office provides baseline support, they need to improve on their capacity to monitor labor market trends and response rate to evolving and seasonal employment needs in order to improve overall service accessibility for enterprise employers. This is supported by the following statements:

“They are helping small businesses in hiring. They just need to improve advertising or informing the people in the area that such stores are hiring so that the people will be aware.”

The employer highlighted that Iriga City PESO support small business by helping them hire employees. However, the office need to improve information dissemination for the jobseekers to be aware what stores are hiring. Better awareness would help connect jobseekers with available opportunities.

Another employer noted that:

“Maybe they can provide frequently asked questions about the queries of applicants if where to submit resume and what are the qualifications etc.”

From the enterprise employer’s response, it is evident that the Iriga City PESO needs to have clearer and more comprehensive information about job vacancies because having such would make the application process easier and more efficient for enterprise employers and jobseekers alike.

The results of this study are parallel with the findings of Flores (2019), who emphasized the importance of understanding the local context and culture when utilizing technology for information dissemination. According to the study, the effectiveness of technological tools largely depends on how well they align with the social, economic, and cultural characteristics of the community they serve. In the case of Iriga City, the local culture is characterized by constant change, particularly in the employment patterns and labor demands. As such, it is imperative for institutions like PESO to continuously adapt their technological strategies to respond to these fluctuating needs in order for them to ensure timely, relevant, and accessible information.

Moreover, the observed limitations in Iriga City PESO’s primary approach to resolving employment vacancies can further be explained by the studies of Evangelista et al. (2025) and Iwayama (2022). These studies highlight that employment services that rely heavily on conventional or narrowly-focused mechanisms mas struggle to address rapidly shifting labor market conditions. Their findings suggest that in order for service delivery to be smooth, flexible, diversified, and context-based employment facilitation strategies are necessary. Taken together, these studies support the notion that though technology is a valuable tool in enhancing accessibility, its effectiveness depends on continuous adaptation, contextual awareness and the capacity of Iriga City PESO to respond proactively to changing labor market realities.

Based on the result, one way to improve on the services of Iriga City PESO is to regularly update its database on the demands of the enterprises within the city. It is also recommended that the office

should track and report on the demographics of the jobseekers which already landed a job to keep their registry of vacancies up to date. Moreover, Iriga City PESO must also look into other ways in resolving the needs of the employers aside from the proven and tested job fairs and mass hirings.

Perceived Effectiveness of the Outcomes Achieved by Iriga City PESO

Table 4 shows the results of the survey to the jobseekers in their assessment of performance management of Iriga City PESO in the outcomes achieved dimension.

Table 4
 Mean score of the perceived effectiveness of Iriga City PESO's services via the jobseekers in terms of outcomes achieved

OUTCOMES ACHIEVED	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
PESO Iriga's services have led to sustained employment for me.	2.87	Substantial Outcomes Achieved
The assistance received from PESO Iriga regarding overseas employment facilitation was helpful in my job search abroad.	2.82	Substantial Outcomes Achieved
The skills trainings and seminars (e.g., Basic Cooking, IT Training) offered by PESO Iriga are relevant to current job market demands and have improved my employability.	2.75	Substantial Outcomes Achieved
PESO Iriga's career coaching activities have helped me make informed career decisions and develop job-seeking capabilities.	2.72	Substantial Outcomes Achieved
Participating in PESO Iriga's programs (e.g., Job Fair, Local Recruitment Activity) has increased my chances of finding employment.	2.66	Substantial Outcomes Achieved
OVERALL MEAN	2.77	Substantial Outcomes Achieved

Note:
 1.00 – 1.49 Limited Outcomes Achieved
 1.50 – 2.49 Partial Outcomes Achieved
 2.50 – 3.49 Substantial Outcomes Achieved
 3.50 – 4.00 Full Outcomes Achieved

The overall assessment of Iriga City PESO's performance in terms of outcomes achieved for jobseekers yielded a mean score of 2.77, which is interpreted as substantial outcomes achieved. This indicates that jobseekers generally perceive the office's services as effective in producing favorable employment-related results. The rating suggests that the assistance provided by the office contributes meaningfully to improving jobseekers' chances of securing employment and progressing toward stable work opportunities. Notably, the most significant finding is the high mean score of 2.87, which reflected a strong level of confidence among jobseekers in the long-term viability of the placements facilitated by Iriga City PESO. This implied that jobseekers do not merely view the placements as temporary solutions, but as opportunities for sustained employment and career growth. Such perceptions highlight the office's effectiveness in matching jobseekers with positions that align with their skills and employment goals.

Overall these findings suggested that Iriga City PESO plays an important role in providing meaningful employment outcomes for jobseekers. The substantial outcome rating underscores the office's contribution to enhancing employment stability and long-term workforce integration. Strengthening existing programs and addressing remaining gaps could further improve the quality and sustainability of employment outcomes achieved through Iriga City PESO's initiatives.

The results are a direct reflection of the increased employment rate in Iriga City when comparing labor statistics prior to and after the institutionalization of the Iriga City PESO. This suggested that the establishment of the office really played a significant role in improving employment outcomes by

providing structured and accessible employment service to jobseekers. The presence of PESO strengthened job matching and referral, recruitment, and workforce development initiatives within the city.

Furthermore, the indicators for outcomes achieved are rated closely to one another, indicating a high level of consistency across the different outcome measure. This close clustering of ratings suggested that the office's services are cohesive and well-aligned. Such consistency reflects a coordinated approach to service delivery, where various programs, projects, and activities collectively contribute to positive employment results.

This cohesive performance may be attributed to the continuous and periodic conduct of job fairs, mass hiring activities, and skills training programs sponsored or facilitated by the office. These activities provide regular opportunities for jobseekers to connect with enterprise employers, enhance their competencies, and improve their employability. As a result, Iriga City PESO's sustained efforts in this dimension likely contribute to the substantial outcomes achieved and the positive perceptions from the jobseekers. These claims are supported by the following responses:

“Malaki rin ang epekto ng mga programa ng PESO Iriga dahil sa madalas nilang pag-imbita o pag-alok ng mga bakanteng trabaho. Kung hindi ka man makuha agad sa unang subok, marahil ay marami pa ang iyong tsansa na sumubok ulit o makapasok sa susunod.”

(The programs of PESO Iriga have a huge impact because they frequently invite or offer job vacancies. In case you are not employed in the first try, there are surely many opportunities to try again or even get hired.)

This highlighted that continuous availability of job openings increases the likelihood of eventually getting employed should the applicant failed to be matched the first time.

Another jobseeker specified that:

“PESO Iriga's career coaching activities influenced me by helping me better understand my strengths and match them with suitable job opportunities.”

It only goes to show that through guidance and advices, the jobseekers gained a clearer understanding of which job opportunities best match their abilities. This kind of support increased their preparedness in pursuing long-term jobs.

Several studies strongly support the findings that job fairs and mass hiring activities are effective activities and programs in employment services. Moroz (2020) and the Global Investment Competitiveness Report 2019/2020: Rebuilding Investor Confidence in Times of Uncertainty (2020) emphasized that these recruitment provide jobseekers with direct and immediate access to a wide range of employment opportunities. By participating in job fairs, jobseekers are able to explore multiple job options, submit applications, and engage in interviews within a relatively short period of time, which reduces the challenges and uncertainties of prolonged job searching. The findings highlight that such activities increase the jobseekers' exposure to potential employers and significantly improve their chance of being hired, particularly in labor markets.

Furthermore, the studies of Minton and Lowe (2019), Monteverde et al. (2025), and Maquilan et al. (2025) underscore the importance of skills training and capacity-building programs in improving jobseekers' employability. Their findings indicate that jobseekers who undergo skills training develop

stronger technical abilities, communication skills, and workplace readiness, making them more confident and competitive in the job market. As shown in the results of the current study, these programs help jobseekers align their skills with the current industry demands, thereby increasing their chances of securing suitable and sustainable employment. Overall, the findings suggested that focusing on both recruitment activities and skills development are crucial in empowering jobseekers and enhancing their employment outcomes.

Based on the results, it would be better is Iriga City PESO would systematically track and report on the duration of employment for hired jobseekers. Additionally, they should also work on continued research on the retention rate of placed jobseekers to measure the quality and sustainability of placements. Aside from that, Iriga City PESO must intensify its Career Guidance and Employment Coaching to focus on soft skills, professionalism, determination, and workplace retention strategies. This ensures that jobseekers are not only technically qualified but are also prepared for the long-term demands of sustainable employment.

Table 5 shows the results of the survey to the enterprise employers in their assessment of performance management of Iriga City PESO in the outcomes achieved dimension.

Table 5
 Mean score of the perceived effectiveness of Iriga City PESO's services via the enterprise employers in terms of outcomes achieved

OUTCOMES ACHIEVED	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
Our enterprise has successfully filled job vacancies through PESO Iriga's services.	2.73	Substantial Outcomes Achieved
PESO Iriga's referral system provides suitable candidates that meet our enterprise's job requirements.	2.65	Substantial Outcomes Achieved
PESO Iriga's assistance contributes to reducing our recruitment costs and time-to-hire.	2.65	Substantial Outcomes Achieved
Partnering with PESO Iriga has positively impacted our workforce quality and productivity.	2.65	Substantial Outcomes Achieved
The candidates referred by PESO Iriga demonstrate improved employability and relevant skills.	2.52	Substantial Outcomes Achieved
OVERALL MEAN	2.64	Substantial Outcomes Achieved

Note:
 1.00 – 1.49 Limited Outcomes Achieved
 1.50 – 2.49 Partial Outcomes Achieved
 2.50 – 3.49 Substantial Outcomes Achieved
 3.50 – 4.00 Full Outcomes Achieved

The overall performance management rating of Iriga City PESO as perceived by enterprise employers is 2.64, which is interpreted as substantial outcomes achieved. This indicated that the office has generally been effective in implementing its employment programs and services, contributing positively to labor market facilitation in the city. The rating reflects enterprise employers' overall satisfaction with Iriga City PESO's role in connecting jobseekers to available employment opportunities. Among the indicators, the highest rated is fulfilling of job vacancies, which obtained a mean rating of 2.73. This results suggested that Iriga City PESO is highly effective in assisting employers in filling their manpower requirements within a reasonable period. The strong performance in this area highlights the

office's efficiency in job matching, coordination with employers and organization of recruitment activities such as fairs and referral services.

On the other hand, the lowest-rated indicator is the quality of referred jobseekers, with a mean score of 2.52. Although this still falls under substantial outcomes achieved, it indicated that enterprise employers suggested that there is a need for improvement in this aspect especially in the preparedness and suitability of applicants endorsed by Iriga City PESO. This finding emphasized the importance of enhancing the screening process, career guidance, and skills training programs to ensure that the referred candidates better meet employer expectations and job requirements.

The results indicated that enterprise employers generally perceive the office as having achieved a significant portion of its intended outputs, particularly in terms of facilitating employment and filling job vacancies. This perception suggests that the office is functioning effectively in meeting its core mandate and responding to the market's needs. Overall, the findings reflected a positive assessment of performance, as employers acknowledge the office's contribution to sustaining workforce availability within the city. However, a closer examination of the quantitative results revealed that the level of effectiveness may be superficial. While job placements are consistently made, the ratings suggested that these outcomes may not be as strong or sustainable as they initially appear. This borderline effectiveness may be attributed to the imbalance between the number of placed jobseekers and the relatively high turnover rate observed among workers. The high turnover rate indicated that many workers do not remain in their positions for a longer duration of time. Although vacancies are quickly filled when employees leave, frequent replacement points to issues related to job satisfaction, job fitness, or employment conditions. As a result, while the office succeeds in placement, the sustainability of employment remains a challenge, highlighting the need for interventions that promote job retention alongside job placement. These findings are supported by the following responses:

"They may have been helpful in providing our needs but most of the applicants do not stay long at work because they do not meet our standard. Sometimes, upon hearing all the requirements we tell them, they do not come back anymore."

The employer implied that in some cases, a mismatch between the referred applicant qualifications but mostly their expectations and the actual demands of the job lead to frequent replacement.

Another employer mentioned that:

"The applicants demonstrate improved skills but sometimes, it is in the attitude of the person being referred to where the problems lie. That is why they do not stay long in their work."

This supported the quantitative results that although the applicants exhibit noticeable improvement in their skills, implying that the skills training and preparation efforts are effective, personal problems such as lack of commitment or professionalism raise serious concerns and issues to the employers.

The findings from the enterprise employers align closely with the studies cited, highlighting both the strengths and limitations of recruitment initiatives. Maloles (2025) noted that even when job fairs and mass hiring events appear successful in placing workers, the actual impact may not fully meet the enterprise employers' expectations. This resonated with the employers' observations that while vacancies

were quickly filled, issues such as high turnover and mismatched job readiness reduce the overall effectiveness of these programs.

Similarly, the studies of Burks et al. (2025) and Gupit et al. (2025) emphasized the importance of job referral systems, showing that applicants who are formally referred have a higher chance of securing employment. From the enterprise employers' perspective, this supports the notion that structured referrals improve the match between jobseekers and available positions, potentially increasing retention compared to applicants who apply independently.

Finally, Hryn (2025) discussed how recruitment activities such as job fairs and referrals help minimize the resources that employers must dedicate to hiring such as time, effort, and recruitment costs. This finding is reflected in the enterprise employers' experiences, as they benefit from a streamlined process where qualified candidates are presented efficiently, reducing the burden of sourcing and screening applicants. Together, these studies illustrate that while recruitment programs are beneficial, employers' concerns about applicant readiness and retention remain key considerations.

Based on the results, the office can improve on achieving their outcomes by collecting post-hiring feedback from enterprise employers within the first three to six months to assess retention and quality issues. This formalized tracking mechanism is critical for understanding true impact. Aside from that, office must also strengthen its pre-screening process by acquiring more detailed requirements from enterprises to ensure the most qualified applicants are referred. Lastly, they may also conduct further studies alongside employers to deeply explore the specific attitudinal and determination issues, allowing them to design highly-targeted interventions for career coaching activities.

Perceived Effectiveness of the Satisfaction with Services by Iriga City PESO

Table 6 shows the results of the survey to the jobseekers in their assessment of performance management of Iriga City PESO in the satisfaction with services dimension.

Table 6

Mean score of the perceived effectiveness of Iriga City PESO's services via the jobseekers in terms of satisfaction with services

SATISFACTION WITH SERVICES	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
I would recommend PESO Iriga's services to other jobseekers.	2.91	High Satisfaction
The staff at PESO Iriga are professional, knowledgeable, and helpful.	2.83	High Satisfaction
The overall quality of services provided by PESO Iriga met my expectations.	2.78	High Satisfaction
My queries and concerns were addressed in a timely manner by PESO Iriga.	2.65	High Satisfaction
I am satisfied with the relevance of the job opportunities referred by PESO Iriga	2.56	High Satisfaction
OVERALL MEAN	2.74	High Satisfaction

Note:

- 1.00 – 1.49 Low Satisfaction
- 1.50 – 2.49 Moderate Satisfaction
- 2.50 – 3.49 High Satisfaction
- 3.50 – 4.00 Exceptional Satisfaction

The findings indicated that jobseekers generally have a high satisfaction level with the services provided by the Iriga City PESO, as reflected in the overall mean rating of 2.74. This suggests that, on average, the jobseekers perceive the office's service as effective and responsive to their employment needs. The strong willingness of jobseekers to recommend the office's services to other applicants underscored their overall positive experience. This indicator received a mean of 2.91. This high recommendation score reflected trust in Iriga City PESO's credibility, service delivery, and support mechanisms. Despite the favorable overall assessment, the lowest-rated indicator pertains to job relevance, which obtained a mean score of 2.56. This result implied that some jobseekers perceive a gap between the job opportunities offered and their personal qualifications, preferences, or career goals. While still falling within the range of high satisfaction, this aspect highlights a potential area for improvement, particularly in matching applicants with more suitable or aligned employment opportunities.

Overall, the results suggested that while Iriga City PESO is performing well in delivering employment services and maintaining client satisfaction, strengthening job matching and relevance could further improve service quality and jobseeker outcomes.

The high level of satisfaction among jobseekers with the services of Iriga City PESO can largely attributed to their positive interactions with the office personnel and the manner in which services are delivered. The finding suggested that jobseekers place significant value on professionalism, approachability, and responsiveness during their engagement with the office. Even when jobseekers are not fully convinced with the fit of the job offers, the quality of interaction and service experience play a crucial role in shaping overall satisfaction. These results extended existing understanding of service satisfaction by highlighting that effective and professional service delivery can compensate for the limitations and gaps in other services. Jobseekers appear willing to recommend Iriga City PESO's services not solely based on successful job placement, but also on how respectfully, efficiently, and supportively they are treated throughout the process. This indicated that high-quality service delivery acts as a mediator against some level of dissatisfaction with job relevance or employment outcomes. Furthermore, the willingness to recommend the Iriga City PESO reflects a level of trust and perceived value in the office's role as a facilitator of employment opportunities. It implies that jobseekers recognize the staffs' efforts and competence, even when external factors, including labor market constraints, limit the availability of ideal job matches. Overall, the findings emphasize the importance of maintaining strong client-service relationships and professional standards, as these significantly influence satisfaction, loyalty, and positive word-of-mouth, independent of perfect outcome fulfillment. These can be supported by the responses including:

"My interactions with the staff at PESO Iriga were generally positive, as they were professional, knowledgeable about the processes, and helpful in guiding me through requirements."

The answer clearly suggested that well-trained, professional, and supportive staff can make processes clearer and less stressful for jobseekers, thereby improving their experience.

Another jobseeker noted that:

"While I hoped for more detailed and long-term job options, their services remain an important support system for jobseekers."

The statement reflected an appreciation of the office as a reliable support system despite unmet expectations in certain areas specifically job matching.

Multiple studies have consistently explained the factors that influence jobseeker's satisfaction with employment-related services. Nguyen et al. (2020) and the Development Academy of the Philippines (DAP, 2019) emphasized that the qualities of good service such as reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and professionalism, are integral to positive client experiences. The results showed that when jobseekers interact with staff who demonstrate these characteristics, they feel respected, supported, and confident in the services being provided, which ultimately leads to higher levels of satisfaction.

In addition to service quality, timeliness is identified as a critical determinant of jobseeker satisfaction. Studies by Jou et al. (2023), Brucal et al. (2022), and Mendoza (2023) highlighted that prompt delivery of services, quick responses to inquiries, and efficient processing of requirements significantly enhance the jobseekers' perceptions of service effectiveness. For them, timely assistance reduces uncertainty and stress during the job search process, reinforcing trust in the institution.

Taken together, these studies suggested that jobseeker satisfaction is shaped not only by employment outcomes but also by the manner of how the services are delivered. High-quality interactions, combined with timely service provision create a positive service environment that fosters satisfaction, trust, and willingness to recommend the service to others.

To further improve its services, the results suggested that Iriga City PESO should document and formalize the staff's best practices in responsiveness and customer service. By institutionalizing these effective practices through clear guidelines, standard operating procedures, and regular training, the office can ensure consistent and high-quality service delivery across all personnel. This approach would help maintain the professionalism and helpfulness that jobseekers value, regardless of which staff member they interact with.

To improve their lapses with job matching, Iriga City PESO may consider strengthening partnerships with a wider range of employers and industries to expand the availability of more detailed and long-term job opportunities. Conducting regular labor market assessments and maintaining an updated database of jobseekers' skills and career preferences can also help improve job matching.

Enterprise Employers' Satisfaction Level on Iriga City PESO's Services

Table 7 shows the results of the survey to the enterprise employers in their assessment of performance management of Iriga City PESO in the satisfaction with services dimension.

Table 7

Mean score of the perceived effectiveness of Iriga City PESO's services via the enterprise employers in terms of satisfaction with services

SATISFACTION WITH SERVICES	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
Communication from PESO Iriga regarding recruitment activities and services is clear and timely.	2.71	High Satisfaction
I would recommend PESO Iriga's services to other employers/enterprises.	2.69	High Satisfaction
The PESO Iriga staff are responsive and professional in addressing our enterprise's needs.	2.67	High Satisfaction
The overall quality of services provided by PESO Iriga met my enterprise's expectations.	2.65	High Satisfaction
I am satisfied with the relevance and quality of candidates referred by PESO Iriga.	2.58	High Satisfaction
OVERALL MEAN	2.66	High Satisfaction

Note:

- 1.00 – 1.49 Low Satisfaction
- 1.50 – 2.49 Moderate Satisfaction
- 2.50 – 3.49 High Satisfaction
- 3.50 – 4.00 Exceptional Satisfaction

The results indicated that enterprise employers generally report a high satisfaction level with the services provided by Iriga City PESO, as reflected in the overall mean rating of 2.66. This suggested that employers view the office as an effective partner in recruitment and employment facilitation, particularly in terms of coordination and support. The highest-rated indicator, clarity and timeliness of communication, with a mean score of 2.71, highlighted the office's strength in maintaining clear, prompt, and effective communication with employers. This finding implied that enterprise employers appreciate being well-informed and promptly assisted throughout the recruitment process, which helps streamline hiring activities and build confidence in the office's services. On the other hand, the lowest-rated indicator, which relates to the quality of referred applicants and obtained a mean of 2.58, suggested a room for improvement in aligning the applicants' qualifications with the enterprises' requirements. While still within the range of high satisfaction, this result indicated that some enterprise employers may perceive gaps in skills, experience, or overall job readiness among referred candidates.

Overall, the findings suggested that while Iriga City PESO excels in communication and coordination, enhancing applicant screening and job matching processes could further improve enterprise employers' satisfaction and ultimately, recruitment outcomes.

The satisfaction level of enterprise employers with the services of Iriga City PESO is generally high. This means that they perceive the services of the office as effective. It can be attributed to two primary factors. The first is the timeliness and relevance of the Iriga City PESO's services and programs. As reflected in the findings, the use of social media platforms enables rapid and efficient dissemination of information, allowing employers to receive updates, announcements, and coordination messages in a timely manner. Provided that internet connectivity and technological literacy are available, this approach enhances accessibility and ensures that services remain responsive to enterprise employers' needs. The second contributing factor to high satisfaction is the professionalism of Iriga City PESO's staff. Enterprise employers perceive that their transactions with the office are handled efficiently, respectfully, and competently. This professionalism fosters smooth coordination, builds trust, and strengthens working relationships between the office and enterprise employers.

Despite these, optimistic perspective, enterprise employers deem that the quality of referred candidates are somehow not up to par with the market's standards. This may be due to a combination of candidate readiness, alignment of skills with job requirements, limited screening or profiling, and expectations management. Addressing these areas could improve the perceived quality of referrals. The following responses support these claims:

"I am not that satisfied because most of the referrals do not proceed to work due to personal reasons."

The employer expressed their sentiments about the referred candidates by the office. The reason mentioned by the employer is due to individual circumstances.

Another response mentioned that:

"The responsiveness and professionalism of the PESO Iriga are generally commendable."

This supported the claim that the staffs' professional conduct helps ensure that concerns and inquiries are addressed clearly and respectfully.

This result is supported by the study of Jou et al. (2023), which emphasized that responsiveness is a critical factor in achieving high levels of customer satisfaction, particularly in service-oriented institutions. Based on the responses, when the enterprise employers receive timely and attentive responses, their confidence in the office increases, leading to more positive service satisfaction.

Similarly, the studies of Mendoza (2023), Diaz et al. (2023), and Real (2025) highlighted that workers' traits have significant influence on customer satisfaction levels. These studies suggest that positive interpersonal interactions can enhance the enterprise employers' overall perception of service quality, even when operational challenges exist.

However, concerns related to job referrals are supported by the findings of Bacay et al. (2025), who identified a mismatch between the skills developed by jobseekers and the skills demanded by employers. This mismatch helped explain why, despite high satisfaction with responsiveness and professionalism, some employers remain less satisfied with the quality of referred applicants.

One effective way to improve the job referral process is by implementing a mandatory follow-up system within a specified period, such as one week until three months after referral, to assess the applicants' compliance, attendance, and initial performance. Systematically collecting this information would allow Iriga City PESO to identify early challenges faced by referred applicants and provide timely guidance or intervention when necessary. This feedback mechanism can also help the office evaluate the effectiveness of its referral screening processes.

In addition, enhancing career guidance and employment coaching services can better prepare applicants mentally and professionally for job placement. By strengthening pre-employment orientation, expectation setting, and workplace readiness training, the office can help ensure that jobseekers are more committed and aligned with employer requirements.

Perceived Effectiveness of the Efficiency of Services of Iriga City PESO

Table 8 shows the results of the survey to the jobseekers in their assessment of performance management of Iriga City PESO in the efficiency of services dimension.

Table 8
Mean score of the perceived effectiveness of Iriga City PESO's services via the jobseekers in terms of efficiency of services

EFFICIENCY OF SERVICES	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
The process for availing of skills training and seminars is efficient.	2.91	Established Efficiency
PESO Iriga effectively utilizes online platforms for job vacancy posting and information dissemination	2.80	Established Efficiency
The time it took from registration to receiving job referrals was reasonable.	2.69	Established Efficiency
PESO Iriga makes optimal use of its resources to deliver employment services.	2.64	Established Efficiency
There are no unnecessary delays or bureaucratic hurdles in accessing PESO Iriga's services.	2.62	Established Efficiency
OVERALL MEAN	2.73	Established Efficiency

Note:
 1.00 – 1.49 Developing Efficiency
 1.50 – 2.49 Emerging Efficiency
 2.50 – 3.49 Established Efficiency
 3.50 – 4.00 Exemplary Efficiency

The findings indicated that Iriga City PESO demonstrates an established level of efficiency in delivering its services, as reflected in the jobseekers' overall average rating of 2.73 under the efficiency of services dimension. This suggests that, in general, jobseekers perceived the office as reasonably effective in carrying out its functions, although there remains room for improvement. Among the indicators of the dimension assessed, applying for skills trainings and seminars sponsored by the office received the highest mean rating of 2.91m indicating that jobseekers find this particular service efficient. This implies that the office's processes related to skills development opportunities are well-managed and easily accessible to clients. Such efficiency is important, as these trainings and seminars enhance employability and align the jobseekers' skills with labor market demands. On the other hand, the lowest-rated indicator, with a mean score of 2.62, pertains to delays in accessing services. Although still within the established efficiency range, the score highlighted a perceived concern among jobseekers regarding waiting times or possibly procedural bottlenecks. Delays may be attributed to factors such as high client volume, limited staffing, or general processes that require streamlining. These inefficiencies affected the jobseekers' perception regarding the office's performance.

Overall, while the efficiency of Iriga City PESO's services is generally viewed positively, addressing issues related to service delays could further enhance jobseekers' experience and strengthen the office's overall performance.

The findings revealed that the efficiency dimension received a relatively high average rating compared to the other service dimensions, with notable strengths observed in the process of availing skill training and seminars among jobseekers. This favorable assessment may be attributed to the integration of digitalized systems as well as strong partnerships with various training providers, all which contribute to faster processing, clearer procedures, and wider access to capacity-building opportunities. These factors likely enhanced jobseekers' perception that the office's training-related services are well-organized, responsive, and effective in addressing their employment needs.

In contrast the efficiency of accessing other services received a comparatively lower rating. This suggested that, despite the overall positive evaluation, certain operational challenges persist. The lower rating may be influenced by a high volume of clients, which can result in longer waiting times and service congestion. Additionally, limited personnel or staffing constraints may hinder the office's ability to promptly attend to all clients. Insufficient resources or facilities, such as inadequate space, equipment, or service counter, may further contribute to delays and reduced efficiency. These constraints can affect the overall service experience of jobseekers, underscoring the need for targeted improvements in resource allocation and service delivery processes to sustain and further enhance Iriga City PESO's efficiency. This can be supported by the following statements from the jobseekers:

"The process from registration to job referral at PESO Iriga was efficient and well-organized. The only delays I experienced were during large job fairs when the volume of applicants was high. Still, the process felt generally smooth and helpful."

The statement implied that the inefficiencies are situational rather than systematic, arising mainly from unusually high client volume rather than poor procedures. Nonetheless, Iriga City PESO's systems and workflows are perceived as efficient.

Another jobseeker noted that:

“Skills training process was efficient and helpful, though limited slots and certificate delays were sometimes the issue.”

The statement praised the general skills training process is perceived as efficient and beneficial, indicating that the procedures for application, participation, and learning are generally well-managed. However, the issues of limited training slots suggested a gap between demand and capacity, which may restrict equal access to opportunities. Additionally, delays in the release of certificates point to logistical constraints that affected timely use of credentials for employment, highlighting areas where service efficiency can still be improved.

Moreno (2023) and Putungan et al. (2022) specifically highlighted how digital platforms and automated systems facilitate faster processing of applications and transactions, thereby reducing waiting time for clients. Their findings support the observation that services such as skills training applications and information access are perceived as efficient, as these processes often benefit from online registration, electronic databases, and digital communication channels. By reducing reliance on manual procedures, technology allows the office to handle a greater volume of clients more effectively.

Similarly, Rodriguez et al. (2025) and Cortez (2023) emphasize that technology enhances the speed and reach of information dissemination and improves the accuracy of data gathering and record management. These improvements contribute to better service delivery and decision-making, as the office can quickly access and update job postings. In relation to the present findings, this explained why efficiency is rated higher in technologically supported service, while areas experiencing delays may indicate limited or uneven application of technological solutions.

Although still rated relatively high-rated, the timeliness of accessing these services suggests an area for improvement. The agency should consider acquiring or developing a modern data-driven management system that is capable of sophisticated skill-to-requirement matching. This ensures that operational efficiency translates into quality job-match outcomes. The staff should also receive continuous capacity building to standardize digital job vacancy postings, ensuring that employers' specific requirements are accurately and clearly captured and inputted into the matching database to minimize discrepancy.

Table 9 shows the results of the survey to the enterprise employers in their assessment of performance management of Iriga City PESO in the efficiency of services dimension.

Table 9

Mean score of the perceived effectiveness of Iriga City PESO's services via the enterprise employers in terms of efficiency of services

EFFICIENCY OF SERVICES	MEAN	INTERPRETATION
The process of requesting and receiving recruitment assistance from PESO Iriga is efficient.	2.85	Established Efficiency
There are no unnecessary delays or bureaucratic hurdles when engaging with PESO Iriga.	2.75	Established Efficiency
PESO Iriga effectively manages the City Skills Registry Database for efficient matching of jobseekers to vacancies.	2.71	Established Efficiency
The time taken by PESO Iriga to facilitate recruitment activities (e.g., Job Fair, Mass Hiring) is reasonable.	2.69	Established Efficiency
PESO Iriga utilizes resources effectively to provide services to employers/enterprises.	2.65	Established Efficiency
OVERALL MEAN	2.73	Established Efficiency

Note:

- 1.00 – 1.49 Developing Efficiency
- 1.50 – 2.49 Emerging Efficiency
- 2.50 – 3.49 Established Efficiency
- 3.50 – 4.00 Exemplary Efficiency

The overall mean score of 2.73 for the efficiency of services of Iriga City PESO, as perceived by enterprise employers, indicated an established level of efficiency. This suggested that from the perspective of employers, the office generally delivers its services in a timely and organized manner, and that its processes are effectively functioning to meet the clients' needs. Among the indicators under this dimension, the highest-rated indicator, with a mean of 2.85, pertains to the process of requesting and receiving assistance from the office. This implied that enterprise employers find the personnel in Iriga City PESO responsive, approachable, and capable of providing the needed support when concerns or service requests are raised. The result reflected positively on the office's frontline service delivery, particularly in terms of communication, coordination, and prompt action, which are crucial in facilitating employer engagement and sustaining partnerships. On the other hand, the lowest-rated indicator received a mean score of 2.65. It pertains to resource management, suggesting that enterprise employers perceive room for improvement in how Iriga City PESO manages its available resources. While efficiency is generally viewed as established, this lower rating indicated that enterprise employers may have observed limitations or gaps in the optimal use or allocation of resources that could affect service delivery. Addressing these concerns may further enhance overall efficiency and strengthen the office's capacity to deliver more effective and sustainable services to its stakeholders.

Overall, the findings highlight that while Iriga City PESO demonstrates commendable efficiency in direct service delivery, particularly in assisting enterprise employers, greater attention to resource management may help increase its efficiency level.

The streamlined process of requesting assistance from Iriga City PESO appears to be the primary reason why enterprise employers rated this indicator as the highest among the indicators of measures of efficiency. These findings suggested that Iriga City PESO has established a well-organized system for

handling service requests, which included clear procedures, effective scheduling and an orderly queuing system. These arrangements most likely minimized waiting time and confusion, enabling employers to access assistance with ease. Moreover, this indicated that the staff of the office are capable of managing client flow efficiently, even during periods of high demand, thereby ensuring that employers receive timely and appropriate support. The implication of this result is that the transaction with enterprise employers is effectively managed by Iriga City PESO Staff. Through this, the office is able to maintain operational efficiency. Altogether, these factors contribute positively to enterprise employers' overall perception of the office, reinforcing confidence in PESO's ability to respond promptly and professionally to their needs.

Conversely, the relatively lower rating for resource management suggested that this aspect of efficiency remains a challenge in Iriga City PESO. Thus may be attributed to the high demand for services alongside limited capacity. Iriga City hosts a wide range of diverse enterprises, each with varying needs and requirements. As a result, processing requests and addressing concerns simultaneously can be difficult, particularly when resources are mismanaged. These can be supported by the following responses from enterprise employers:

"The efficiency of the process of requesting and receiving recruitment assistance from PESO Iriga is generally good."

Another employer mentioned that:

"[The City Skills Registry Database] is not 100% match but their efforts in providing job matching services is great."

The enterprise employer emphasized Iriga City PESO's commitment in actively supporting employment services but noted that there is a room for improvement in its matching processes.

The results of the present survey are consistent with the findings of Gangoso (2023), who highlighted that an organized workflow and well-defined processes play a crucial role in enhancing organizational efficiency. The alignment of these findings suggested that structured procedures, clear task distribution, and systematic delivery of service significantly contribute to the enterprise employers' positive perceptions of efficiency.

Similarly, the study is supported by Enda (2025), who emphasized that workflows must not only be well-designed but also carefully planned and effectively executed to achieve optimal efficiency. This reinforces the idea that efficiency is not merely a result of having procedures in place, but of ensuring that these procedures and protocols are implemented consistently. The effective execution of workflow processes allows organizations to respond promptly to enterprise employer needs while minimizing delays and operational bottlenecks.

Moreover, the findings are further supported by Cortez (2023), who underscored the importance of good resource management in achieving service efficiency. Cortez noted that the appropriate allocation and usage of resources are essential to support service delivery. In the context of this study, the observed challenges in resource management reflect the critical need to balance service demand with available capacity.

Some ways to improve the services of Iriga City PESO is by implementing transparent resource allocation. This can be done when criteria for distributing manpower, training slots, and proper budget

allocation is developed as well as prioritizing high-impact services such as job placement, job matching, and skills trainings. Another way is to introduce monitoring and evaluation systems which is the main goal of this study.

Comparison between the Perceived Effectiveness of Jobseekers and Enterprise Employers regarding Iriga City PESO's Services

Table 10 shows the summarized results of the independent t-test, comparing the jobseekers and enterprise employers' perceived effectiveness of the services of Iriga City PESO.

Table 10

Jobseekers' and enterprise employers' differences in the four dimensions of the performance management of Iriga City PESO

Performance Management Dimensions	Jobseekers		Enterprise Employers		t	df	p
	M	SD	M	SD			
Accessibility	2.66	1.07	2.70	1.11	1.96	493	0.72
Outcomes Achieved	2.77	1.02	2.64	1.13	1.97	465	0.14
Satisfaction with Services	2.74	1.03	2.66	1.12	1.97	472	0.31
Efficiency of Services	2.73	1.05	2.73	1.10	1.96	489	0.99

Note. M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, t = t-critical (two-tailed), df = degrees of freedom, p = p-value (two-tailed). p < 0.05 indicates statistical significance.

An independent sample t-test was used to compare the jobseekers' and enterprise employers' perceived effectiveness of Iriga City PESO's performance management in terms of the four dimensions. The results were as followed:

Accessibility

T-test revealed that there is no statistically significant difference between the perceptions of jobseekers and enterprise employers regarding the accessibility of Iriga City PESO's services. Jobseekers reported a mean perception score of 2.66 (SD = 1.07), while enterprise employers reported a slightly higher mean perception score of 2.66 (SD = 1.11). Despite this small numerical difference, the computed p-value of 0.72 exceeds the set alpha level 0.05, indicating that the difference is not statistically significant.

The findings suggests that both groups generally share a similar view of how accessible Iriga City PESO's services are, implying consistency in service reach, availability, and ease of access as experienced by different stakeholders.

Outcomes Achieved

With respect to outcomes achieved, the results likewise indicated no significant difference in perceived effectiveness between the two groups. Jobseekers obtained a mean score of 2.77 (SD = 1.02), while enterprise employers reported a mean score of 2.64 (SD = 1.13) Although jobseekers rated this dimension slightly higher, the computed p-value of 0.14 is greater than the alpha level of 0.05, confirming that the observed difference is not statistically significant.

This implies that both jobseekers and enterprise employers have comparable assessments of the extent to which Iriga City PESO's services achieve their intended outcomes, such as successful job matching, employment facilitation, or workforce support.

Satisfaction with Services

In terms of satisfaction with services, the independent sample t-test also yielded no statistically significant difference between the two groups. Jobseekers recorded a mean score of 2.74 (SD = 1.03), while enterprise employers reported a mean score of 2.66 (SD = 1.12). The computed p-value of 0.31 exceeds the alpha level of 0.05, indicating that the difference in satisfaction levels is not significant.

This result suggests that both jobseekers and enterprise employers are similarly satisfied with the services provided by Iriga City PESO, reflecting a generally uniform perception of service quality, responsiveness, and overall experience across clientele.

Efficiency of Services

Finally, the analysis of efficiency of services showed identical mean scores for both jobseekers and enterprise employers ($M = 2.73$), with standard deviations of 1.05, and 1.10, respectively. The computed p-value of 0.99 is far greater than the alpha level of 0.05, strongly indicating the absence of a statistically significant difference between the two groups.

This finding demonstrates that jobseekers and enterprise employers perceive the efficiency of Iriga City PESO's services in the same manner, suggesting a shared assessment of how well resources, time, and processes are managed in service delivery.

It is once again reiterated that since purposive sampling was used in this study, these results cannot represent the entire population of jobseekers and enterprise employers.

The results indicated that both jobseekers and enterprise employers share similar experiences regarding the services provided by Iriga City PESO in the four dimensions of performance management. This similarity in perception may be due to the consistency of the service delivery of the office. They follow standard practices mandated by policies and guidelines, ensuring that the services remain uniform across their main clients. As a result, services are experienced comparably between jobseekers and enterprise employers. When services are delivered consistently, clients are more likely to form similar impressions of service quality, effectiveness, and efficiency. The uniformity of PESO's processes minimizes variability in client experience, which helps explain why no significant differences were observed in the perceptions of the two groups.

These results are further supported by the studies of Iwayama (2022), Bachita and Bayoneta (2021), Fredriksson (2020), and Bayudan-Dacuyucuy et al. (2024), which collectively discuss the inherent nature of employment services as a dual-client system. These studies emphasize that jobseekers and employers are interdependent clients, such that when one group benefits from employment service, the other gains as well, directly or indirectly. For instance, successful job placement not only addresses the employment needs of jobseekers while simultaneously fulfilling enterprise employers' demands for labor force. This reciprocal relationship helped explain why both clients tend to report similar experiences and perceptions of service effectiveness. The literature also highlighted that employment service outcomes are shared. When jobseekers are matched efficiently with appropriate positions, employers benefit from reduced recruitment time and improved workforce quality. Conversely, when employers provide clear job

requirements and opportunities, jobseekers experience smoother placement processes. This interconnected relationship reinforces the synchronization of perceptions observed in the study, as both client groups evaluated the office's performance based on comparable outcomes and shared service experiences.

Moreover, the findings suggested that while current processes are already established and functioning effectively, there remains potential for further improvement. Several studies, including those of Ahmad et al. (2024), Sucaldito et al. (2025), Dela Cruz (2020), and Ongcal and Tamayo (2025), underscore the importance of adopting a clear and well-defined working framework to enhance service delivery. These authors argue that a framework provides structure, direction, and consistency, ensuring that services are delivered uniformly regardless of client. By institutionalizing a standardized framework, Iriga City PESO can further strengthen process consistency, improve coordination, and sustain equitable service delivery, thereby enhancing overall effectiveness and efficiency.

Sustainable Framework for Action (SFA) for PESO Iriga City

The third objective of this research is to propose a context-specific sustainable development framework for enhanced program implementation framed through the International Labour Organization's (ILO) Performance Measurement Framework (PMF). The resulting framework, the Sustainable Framework for Action (SFA) for Iriga City PESO, is designed to move the service delivery focus beyond immediate outputs towards achieving verifiable, long-term outcomes and impacts on local employment which is sustainable employment.

The quantitative results were utilized to identify the dimension of performance management that needs improvement. Since all the dimensions garnered in a fairly high rating from the perceptions of jobseekers and enterprise employers, the data from the structured interview were analyzed using thematic analysis.

Thematic Analysis of Jobseekers and Enterprise Employers' Experiences with Iriga City PESO's Services focusing on Accessibility

Based on the responses in the interview, there are three (3) major recurring themes with respect to the accessibility dimension.

Table 11 shows the result of thematic analysis for the accessibility dimension of the performance management of Iriga City PESO.

Table 11

Themes generated from responses of jobseekers and enterprise employers regarding the accessibility of the services of Iriga City PESO

Themes	Supporting Statements
	<i>"Easy to browse information on Facebook page."</i>
High dependence of social media as the primary communication channel.	<i>"[Their] most effective digital channel is their Facebook page."</i> <i>"All information is on their FB page."</i> <i>"Very clear posts with qualifications and requirements."</i>
Clear and detailed job vacancy information provided.	<i>"Bulletin posts show the number of available jobs."</i> <i>"Complete and detailed job vacancy postings."</i>
High accessibility of PESO services but inconsistent responsiveness.	<i>"They don't respond immediately to messages."</i> <i>"Sometimes [the office] lack responsiveness."</i> <i>"Staff are accommodating."</i>

The first theme highlighted the office's strong preference for using social media, particularly its Facebook page, as the primary platform for disseminating information. Both jobseekers and enterprise employers view Iriga City PESO's active presence on Facebook positively, as it provides a fast, accessible, and convenient way to receive job postings and other relevant updates. This channel allows clients to stay informed in real time without the need for frequent physical visits to the office, thereby enhancing overall accessibility.

Despite these advantages, jobseekers pointed out that physical and digital barriers may affect the effectiveness of this communication channel. Limited access to smartphones and/or stable internet connectivity can restrict some individuals from full benefiting from online announcements. Similarly, enterprise employers expressed the need for a greater variety of communication channels when engaging with the office. While Facebook is viewed as useful, enterprise employers often require more formal or direct means of communication particularly for concerns that demand detailed discussion or documentation.

The second theme centers on how jobseekers access information about job vacancies, with particular emphasis on the clarity and quality of Iriga City PESO's job postings. Jobseekers strongly expressed appreciation for how information is presented, noting that postings are generally clear, well-structured, and easy to understand. With sufficient details readily available, jobseekers are able to filter opportunities more efficiently, reducing uncertainty and saving time that might otherwise be spent on unsuitable applications.

Enterprise employers similarly expressed positive views regarding this aspect of Iriga City PESO's service. They acknowledged that the office ensures job postings remain relevant and aligned with the specific needs of their enterprises. By carefully presenting accurate and appropriate information, the

office helps employers attract applicants who are more likely to meet their qualifications, thereby improving the efficiency of the recruitment process.

The final theme highlights the clients' overall experiences in interacting with Iriga City PESO's staff, particularly in terms of approachability and responsiveness. Most clients described the staff as easy to approach. This suggested that staff are generally perceived as accommodating, friendly, and willing to assist, which contributes positively to clients' comfort and trust when engaging with the office.

Despite this positive assessment, numerous remarks point to concerns regarding the responsiveness of the staff, especially in digital communication. Users noted instances of delayed replies, unanswered inquiries, and inconsistent information when communication is conducted through messaging applications or other online platforms. Strengthening customer service mechanisms would not only improve responsiveness but also ensure consistency in information delivery.

Thematic analysis of Iriga City PESO's performance in terms of accessibility shows that the employment office delivers services that are generally accessible, helpful, and informative, especially through its strong social media presence. Jobseekers and enterprise employers appreciate the clarity and completeness of job postings, as well as the presence of job fairs. However, recurring issues emerged particularly about the inconsistent responsiveness and limitations of the dependence on the use of social media. While many clients have positive experiences, their responses indicates a need for improved communication systems, broader information dissemination, and more engagement or interaction with the jobseekers and enterprise employers to ensure equitable access to the office's services.

Thematic Analysis of Jobseekers and Enterprise Employers' Experiences with Iriga City PESO's Services focusing on Outcomes Achieved

Table 12 shows the result of thematic analysis for the outcomes achieved dimension of the performance management of Iriga City PESO.

Table 12

Themes generated from responses of jobseekers and enterprise employers regarding the outcomes achieved of the services of Iriga City PESO

Themes	Supporting Statements
Enhancing employability and job readiness through skills training and career coaching.	"Their trainings made me more computer literate and I learned new skills which helped me on my current job." "TESDA-aligned trainings were directly tied to in-demand roles... participants secured jobs after certification." "[Employees] have the skills that we need." "Maraming options at opportunities dahil sa job fairs."
Iriga City PESO's referral and job matching system is functional but inconsistent.	(There are many options and opportunities due to job fairs.) "Moderately effective... sometimes they provide suitable individuals." "[Referred] Applicants do not stay long... they don't meet our standard."

Both jobseekers and enterprise employers acknowledge the Iriga City PESO plays a critical role in improving job readiness through their various projects, programs, and/or activities. It is usually through a form of technical skills training, career coaching, and pre-employment guidance. Such interventions contribute to improving applicants' competencies, confidence, and awareness of workplace expectations, thereby increasing their employability. Enterprise employers in particular, acknowledge the value of these programs in producing applicants who possess the basic technical qualifications required for available positions.

However, despite these positive contributions, both groups noted existing gaps, particularly in areas related to work experience and soft skills. Employers pointed out that some applicants still lack competencies such as communication, teamwork, adaptability, and professional work ethics, while jobseekers expressed the need for more exposure to real-world work environments. These findings suggested the need for additional trainings and seminars that place greater emphasis on soft-skills development, experiential learning, and practical workplace simulations. Addressing these gaps may further strengthen the office's role in improving job readiness and ensure that jobseekers are more holistically prepared for employment.

The second theme revealed that while jobseekers generally report positive experiences with Iriga City PESO's services, enterprise employers express more mixed evaluations. This contrast highlights a noticeable disconnect between the two client groups. Jobseekers often associate the office opportunities with successful or promising employment outcomes, whereas enterprise employers describe the results of applicant referrals as highly variable, ranging from effective and suitable matches to opportunities are being created and accessed, their translation into consistently successful employer outcomes remains uneven. Taken together, the theme generated in this dimension indicated that Iriga City PESO has made significant progress in developing strong human capital development programs. These efforts are largely reflected in skills training, capacity-building activities, and other interventions which aim to enhance jobseekers' employability. Such programs appear to effectively prepare jobseekers and positively shape their perceptions of the office's role in supporting employment processes.

However, despite these strengths, a notable gap exists. To be specific, Iriga City PESO's job matching function and applicant referral system do not fully maximize the benefits of its human capital development initiatives. Possible contributing factors include inconsistencies in employer partnerships, variations in the quality of referrals, and misalignment between jobseekers' competencies and employer's expectations. These gaps may limit the effectiveness of referrals and weaken enterprise employers' confidence in the matching process.

Strengthening partnerships with enterprise employers therefore plays a critical role in bridging this gap. Closer collaboration can help Iriga City PESO better understand enterprise employers' evolving needs, improve referral accuracy, and align training programs with labor market demands. By reinforcing enterprise employer engagement and refining its referral mechanisms, Iriga City PESO can ensure that enhanced job readiness among jobseekers translates into effective, efficient, and sustainable employment outcomes for both clients.

Thematic Analysis of Jobseekers and Enterprise Employers' Experiences with Iriga City PESO's Services focusing on Satisfaction with Services

Table 13 shows the result of thematic analysis for the outcomes achieved dimension of the performance management of Iriga City PESO.

Table 13

Themes generated from responses of jobseekers and enterprise employers regarding the satisfaction with services of Iriga City PESO

Themes	Supporting Statements
Service quality is generally positive but limited by operational gaps.	"They are trying their best to provide quality services, but they definitely need improvement."
	"Helpful in my job search, but I hope for more detailed options."
	"8/10... [the staff] are active but not quite."
Recommendations are driven by convenience, accessibility, and staff helpfulness but hindered by inconsistency.	"Competent, efficient, and trustworthy personnel but the candidates they referred are inconsistent."
	"Highly recommended... maayos at malinaw ang serbisyo."
	(Highly recommended... the services are decent and clear.)
	"Improve [on] digitization of processes."

The responses revealed a certain level of ambiguity, as respondents initially expressed general satisfaction with Iriga City PESO's services but later described specific mishaps and shortcomings. This pattern, alongside the quantitative data, suggested that while the overall service quality is perceived as good and helpful, underlying operational issues remain evident to clients. Such concerns include limited job variety, occasional delays in processing or communication, and weak floor-through on certain requests or referrals, which create gaps between expectations and actual service delivery. These findings indicated that Iriga City PESO's primary strength lies in the professionalism, approachability, and helpfulness of its staff. Clients appear to value the positive interactions and most especially the willingness of personnel to assist, which significantly contributes to their overall satisfaction. However, these positive experiences are sometimes outweighed by operational constraints that affect service consistency and efficiency.

The presence of these gaps pointed to the need for targeted improvements in operational efficiency and program development. Enhancing internal processes, improving response times. Expanding job opportunities and strengthening employer-focused programs could help address recurring concerns. By complementing staff professionalism with more streamlined and efficient systems, more diverse and employer-responsive initiatives, Iriga City PESO may reach higher and more sustained levels of satisfaction among both jobseekers and enterprise employers.

The second theme focused on how Iriga City PESO's services are experienced and recommended by its clients. Along the same lines of the first theme, it emphasized that while the office's services are generally viewed as recommendable, there are notable considerations that clients believe need to be improved upon. Both jobseekers and enterprise employers expressed willingness to recommend the office's relevance and overall contribution to employment.

However, similar to the first theme, respondents also identified areas that require improvement, particularly regarding the consistency of service. Even though the office is widely appreciated for its role as a bridge between jobseekers and enterprise employers, lapses in communication, delayed responses, and inconsistency in the quality of applicant referrals were frequently cited concerns. These issues tend to disrupt the otherwise positive experiences of clients and prevent universal or unqualified satisfaction.

Basically, the first theme focuses on the delicate balance between the strengths and weaknesses in Iriga City PESO's service delivery while the second theme works on how the strengths lead to recommendations, while the weaknesses discourage it. The better the office's service quality and operational consistency, the more likely are the clients going to recommend it. On the other hand, the more gaps and problems persist, the more hesitant the clients become. These themes cover Iriga City PESO's strong foundation, positive impact, and significant trust. But for the clients to be exceptionally satisfied, system improvements must be worked upon. Overall, the findings suggested that Iriga City PESO is perceived as a valuable but uneven service provider. Its core mandate and function are clearly acknowledged and supported by jobseekers and enterprise employers alike, yet operational inconsistencies hinder its ability to consistently meet expectations. Addressing these gaps, especially in communication, responsiveness, and referral accuracy, may help the office to strengthen their reliability and ensure that recommendations of its services are due to greater confidence and higher levels of client satisfaction.

Thematic Analysis of Jobseekers and Enterprise Employers' Experiences with Iriga City PESO's Services focusing on Efficiency of Services

Table 14 shows the result of thematic analysis for the outcomes achieved dimension of the performance management of Iriga City PESO.

Table 14
 Themes generated from responses of jobseekers and enterprise employers regarding the efficiency of services of Iriga City PESO

Themes	Supporting Statements
Inconsistent effectiveness of job matching and the skills registry database	<p>"It helps us find qualified candidates in a short period of time."</p> <p>"I believe Iriga City PESO's management of the City Skills Registry Database is moderately effective."</p> <p>"Matching could be improved."</p> <p>"[The time it takes is] very reasonable. They have a strategic process for recruitment activities."</p>
Timeliness of recruitment and referral processes	<p>"Hindi naman nagtagal ang pagitan mula sa pagpaparehistro hanggang sa job referral."</p> <p>(The interval between registration and job referral did not last long.)</p> <p>"[The process] could be faster for urgent staffing needs."</p> <p>"They leverage online platforms and local partnerships to connect to jobseekers."</p>
Moderately effective resource utilization but excellent use of online platforms.	<p>"Very effective! They post updated job vacancy postings and information needed."</p> <p>"Although majority has access to Facebook, there are still areas in the city with poor internet connectivity."</p>

The first theme underscored the functionality and utility of the system by highlighting the generally positive remarks regarding its use by the office. Jobseekers, in particular, appreciate its role in facilitating job matching, as it allows them to be connected with enterprises with job vacancies that are relevant to their skills and other qualifications. From their perspective, the system serves as a helpful tool in narrowing down employment opportunities and supporting a more focused job search. In contrast, enterprise employers express reservations about the effectiveness of applicant-job alignment.

Even though they acknowledge the database's potential, they believe that the matching process can still be refined to better meet their specific job requirements. Enterprise employers' feedback suggested that some referrals may not fully align with either job qualifications, experience levels, or organizational expectations, leading to mixed perceptions of the database's overall effectiveness.

The findings further suggested that the database's utility can be enhanced through more proactive engagement and continuous partnerships with key stakeholders. Regular consultation with enterprise employers, closer coordination with industry partners, and the integration of up-to-date labor market information could greatly help ensure that matching criteria remain relevant and responsive to actual demand. Additionally, increasing awareness of emerging industry trends and labor market shifts would enable the office to refine its matching processes, ultimately improving alignment, satisfaction, and employment outcomes for both jobseekers and enterprise employers.

The second theme reflected that overall, both the jobseekers and enterprise employers perceive the recruitment and referral activities of Iriga City PESO as timely and well organized. Most clients find the processing time reasonable, indicating that established procedures and workflows are generally effective in facilitating recruitment and job placement. This reflected a level of dependability in the office's operations, as both client groups can typically expect services to be delivered within an acceptable timeframe.

However, respondents also noted that during peak seasons, particularly when multiple enterprises require a large number of employees at the same time, the recruitment and referral process may become congested. Increased demand during these periods can take a toll in existing systems and resources, resulting in slower processing and reduced responsiveness. These instances highlighted the limitations of the current operational capacity when faced with sudden or high-volume recruitment needs.

Despite these challenges, the findings suggested that Iriga City PESO's recruitment and referral activities remain generally reliable. Enhancing operational flexibility and developing contingency plans for seasonal surges, such as temporary staffing adjustments, advanced scheduling, or demand forecasting, could help mitigate the bottleneck effect. Implementing these measures may further improve efficiency, ensure service continuity during high-demand periods, and strengthen overall client satisfaction.

Responses indicated that Iriga City PESO generally demonstrates strategic and effective utilization of its resources, particularly in the way it disseminates information to its stakeholders. Through the use of digital platforms, the office is able to extend the reach of its services to geographically-challenged or remote areas, allowing jobseekers and enterprise employers to access announcements, job postings, and other relevant updates without the need for frequent visits to the office. This approach reflected efficient resource use by maximizing existing tools to broaden service coverage.

However, the effectiveness of this strategy remains dependent on several external factors, including clients' digital literacy, the availability and reliability of internet connection, and access to

appropriate devices. Clients who lack these resources may still experience barriers to information access, which can limit the inclusivity of the office's services despite their efforts to extend their reach.

These findings suggested that while current practices are generally effective, improvements in responsiveness and the diversification of information dissemination platforms could further enhance service equity. Expanding communication channels to include a mix of both online and offline methods, strengthening response mechanisms, and tailoring outreach strategies to different client capacities may help ensure that all stakeholders, regardless of location or digital access, can benefit equally from the office's services.

The efficiency and effectiveness of Iriga City PESO's services depend on the interconnection among well-maintained skills database, timely facilitation of recruitment activities, and strategic use of digital and institutional resources. Improving the applicant-job matching, ensuring timely communication, and enhancing the resource utilization, or simply by strengthening any of the components would reinforce the overall services of the office. By doing so, enterprise employers are ensured to find suitable candidates quickly and jobseekers are able to access relevant opportunities efficiently.

The Proposed Sustainable Framework for Action (SFA) for Iriga City PESO

The central tenet of this SFA is that the ultimate measure of successfulness is the outcome and the resulting impact. From the collected quantitative and qualitative data, the components of the framework were generated. It systematically links various stages of program operation to their ultimate societal impact and is structured around four interconnected elements: Input, Output, Outcome, and Impact.

Table 15 below shows the summary of the combined quantitative and qualitative data supporting the components of the input element of the SFA.

Table 15

Summary of quantitative and qualitative results for the components of input of the SFA

SFA Input	Quantitative Data	Generated Themes
Database System	Outcomes Achieved: M _{Jobseekers} = 2.77 (Substantial Outcomes Achieved) M _{EnterpriseEmployers} = 2.64 (Substantial Outcomes Achieved)	Outcomes Achieved: Iriga City PESO's referral and job matching system is functional but inconsistent.
	Efficiency of Services: M _{Jobseekers} = 2.73 (Established Efficiency) M _{EnterpriseEmployers} = 2.73 (Established Efficiency)	Efficiency of Services: Inconsistent effectiveness of job matching and the skills registry database.
Human Capital Training	Outcomes Achieved: M _{Jobseekers} = 2.77 (Substantial Outcomes Achieved) M _{EnterpriseEmployers} = 2.64 (Substantial Outcomes Achieved)	Outcomes Achieved: Enhancing employability and job readiness through skills training and career coaching.
	Satisfaction with Services: M _{Jobseekers} = 2.74 (High Satisfaction) M _{EnterpriseEmployers} = 2.66 (High Satisfaction)	Satisfaction with Services: Service quality is generally positive but limited by operational gaps.
Operational Resources	Accessibility: M _{Jobseekers} = 2.67 (Moderately Accessible) M _{EnterpriseEmployers} = 2.70 (Moderately Accessible)	Accessibility: High dependence of social media as the primary communication channel.
	Efficiency of Services: M _{Jobseekers} = 2.73 (Established Efficiency) M _{EnterpriseEmployers} = 2.73 (Established Efficiency)	Efficiency of Services: Moderately effective resource utilization but excellent use of online platforms.

The findings show that both jobseekers and enterprise employers perceived outcomes achieved as substantial, with jobseekers reporting a mean of 2.77 and enterprise employers a mean of 2.64. Similarly, efficiency of services is rated at an established level by both groups with identical mean of 2.73. These data, together with the theme “Iriga City PESO’s referral and job matching system is functional but inconsistent” for outcomes achieved and “Inconsistent effectiveness of job matching and the skills registry database” for efficiency of services, indicated that while Iriga City PESO is performing well in delivering results and managing services, there remains a clear gap needed to be addressed in order to further strengthen and systematize its processes.

A modern Database System can either supplement the existing City Skills Registry Database or replace it entirely, depending on its design, scope, and capacity. Such system would address the observed gaps in referral quality, applicant-job alignment, and responsiveness by integrating real-time data on jobseekers’ skills, training backgrounds, work experience, vis-à-vis the enterprise employers’ constantly evolving labor demands. This proposed action necessitates sustained funding for a modern, data-driven skills matching system. This system should not only capture currently available skills among jobseekers but also continuously incorporate up-to-date labor market information, industry trends, and enterprise requirements. By doing so, the office can build on the already substantial outcomes achieved and elevate established efficiency to exemplary level. Anchored on the study’s findings, such initiative would strengthen Iriga City PESO’s job matching and referral functions, enhance efficiency during both regular and peak periods, and ensure that the substantial outcomes already achieved are made more effective, equitable, and sustainable for both jobseekers and enterprise employers.

Another key component of the input of the SFA is derived from the conglomerated results of the quantitative data of the outcomes achieved and satisfaction with the services. The data for the former was already presented. The data for satisfaction with services are likewise rated highly by both groups with a mean score of 2.74 for jobseekers and 2.66 for enterprise employers. These results are supported by the themes “Enhancing employability and job readiness through skills training and career coaching” for outcomes achieved and “Service quality is generally positive but limited by operational gaps” for satisfaction with services. All of which suggested that the office’s clients generally value quality, professionalism and support provided by the staff, despite recognizing that certain operational gaps limit full potential of these services.

To build on these strengths, Human Capital Training programs should be further refined by placing stronger emphasis on soft skills development, professionalism, determination, and workplace retention strategies. Feedback from enterprise employers highlighted persistent gaps in communication skills, work ethics, adaptability, and long-term commitment, which are essential for sustained employment but are not always sufficiently addressed by technical trainings alone. Integrating modules on interpersonal skills, workplace behavior, career resilience, and retention-focused preparation into existing training programs would help ensure that jobseekers are not only employable but also capable of thriving and remaining productive in the workplace. By aligning human capital development more closely with employer expectations and real-world work environments, Iriga City PESO can transform substantial outcomes and high satisfaction levels into more durable, efficient, and sustainable employment outcomes for both jobseekers and enterprise employers.

The last salient component of the input of the SFA is based on the quantitative findings and qualitative analysis of the results of accessibility and efficiency of services. Quantitative results showed that jobseekers ($M = 2.67$) and enterprise employers (2.70) rated accessibility as moderately accessible,

suggesting that services are generally reachable but there are certain barriers. In contrast, efficiency of services is perceived as established by both groups with equal mean scores of 2.73. These, together with the theme “High dependence of social media as the primary communication channel” for accessibility and “Moderately effective resource utilization but excellent use of online platforms” for efficiency of services highlighted the need to strengthen resource allocation and utility to ensure that services are consistently accessible to all clients.

To address these concerns, the Operational Resources is proposed. This entails that integration of technology must go beyond just being an auxiliary tool, instead, it must be institutionalized as a core component of Iriga City PESO’s operational framework. This integration should clearly be articulated in the office’s Citizen’s Charter to ensure transparency, accountability, and consistency in service delivery. Standardized digital communication protocols, such as defined response timelines, designated platforms for specific services, and clear points of contact can help reduce inconsistencies and improve efficiency. Additionally, expanding information dissemination channels to include a balanced mix of online and offline platforms would ensure that services remain inclusive, specifically for clients with limited or intermittent internet connection or challenged digital literacy.

Equally important is sustained funding to support the continuous upgrading of technological infrastructure and systems. Investments in reliable databases, communication tools, and monitoring systems would allow Iriga City PESO to manage information more efficiently and respond to client needs more promptly. Alongside this, continuous training and capacity-building for personnel are essential to ensure that staff are competent, confident and adaptable in using technology as part of daily operations. Regular training programs can also help staff to keep up with changing digital tools and service delivery standards. By embedding technology integration, funding support, and personnel development into its core operations, Iriga City PESO can strengthen both accessibility and efficiency, ultimately delivering a more responsive, equitable, and sustainable services to jobseekers and enterprise employers.

Altogether, these inputs aim to increase the overall effectiveness of the services of Iriga City PESO. Figure 4 shows the proposed framework.

Figure 4: Sustainable Framework for Action

From the inputs, the following outputs were deduced: Operational Efficiency, Matching Quality, and Extensive Programming.

Operational Efficiency ensures that the process from registration to referral remains efficient, smooth, and well-organized, with no unnecessary steps, utilizing effective digital and in-person channels. Thematic analysis show that this process is generally efficient and well-organized so minimal changes is proposed.

Matching Quality demands strengthening the pre-screening processes by assessing the skill level of applicants and deciding as to what enterprise would benefit the most from their skill level. Feedback from clients, specifically employers suggested a tighter pre-screening process that is why it is incorporated in this framework.

Extensive Programming demands that the current platform used must still be maintained. However, comments from jobseekers as well as enterprise employers implies the need to adopt a multi-platform strategy. Incorporating this to the framework would ensure fair and equitable access to services including minorities and people with disabilities.

The outcomes of the framework include: Candidate Tracking, Employability Enhancement, and Inclusivity and Access.

Candidate Tracking compels the office to implement a follow-up system (within one week of referral) to ascertain the reason for withdrawal or non-submission of requirements by candidates, providing necessary guidance or intervention if possible. Once resolved, a systematic tracking and reporting of the placed jobseekers within the duration of employment (retention) would be conducted. This must include collecting post-hiring feedback from enterprises within the first three to six months to assess the employees' quality and retention issues, if there are any. This is a direct answer to the feedback from enterprise employers about the high turnover rates of placed jobseekers via job fairs and mass hirings conducted by Iriga City PESO.

Employability Enhancement necessitates the successful increase in the jobseekers' confidence and job-seeking skills (soft skills/professionalism), which guarantees placements in jobs for which they were trained. Since feedback from jobseekers in this aspect is generally positive, minimal change is needed.

Inclusivity and Access means that the reach of Iriga City PESO's information dissemination can now reach far-flung areas as well as those places that are geographically challenged. Aside from physical barriers, this also connects the employment office to the jobseekers and enterprise employers with varying digital familiarity level by utilizing multi-platform systems.

All of these actions within the proposed framework incorporate the data gathered from the survey and structured interview. By meticulously analyzing them and forming linkages among the data, the impact, which is sustainable employment would be achieved. This is congruent to one of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by the United Nations, specifically goal 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth. The SDG 8 brings importance to how countries all over the world need to promote economic growth and development. Iriga City PESO's services, by implementing this framework, would have a more structured procedure that acts as a guide in achieving this goal.

VI. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This study is a comprehensive evaluation of the employment services provided by the Iriga City PESO focusing on the Performance Management aspect. This study also proposed a Sustainable Framework for Action based on the underpinnings of the delivery framework of the ILO. The respondents are the 2024 jobseekers in Iriga City and enterprise employers duly registered within the city. The course of this study ran from January to December 2025. This study only focused on the perceived effectiveness of the jobseekers and enterprise employers about the four of the Performance Management elements of the ILO namely, Accessibility, Outcomes Achieved, Satisfaction with Services, and Efficiency of Service. This study employed a mixed method of research specifically the convergent parallel design method.

The other elements of the delivery framework provided by ILO are not part of the focus of this study since the employment office already satisfied them based on their annual accomplishment report. To avoid observational bias in the perceived effectiveness of the operations of Iriga City PESO, its employees were not selected as the target population of this study. The impact of the proposed SFA is not evaluated in this study due to the limited time frame as well as the lack of legal basis that compels the employment office to religiously follow the proposed SFA.

VII. CONCLUSION

Conclusion A

Research Objective 1: Describe the Jobseekers and Enterprise Employers' perceived effectiveness level of performance management of Iriga City PESO's employment services in terms of the four dimensions: Accessibility, Outcomes Achieved, Satisfaction with Services, and Efficiency of Service.

Based on the findings, the jobseekers and enterprise employers' perceived effectiveness of the services of Iriga City PESO is the office is performing at a consistently strong and reliable level across the four key dimensions of performance management by ILO. The combined perceptions of the office's main clients, the jobseekers and enterprise employers, suggested that Iriga City PESO's services are implemented in a uniform manner, resulting to comparable client experiences despite differing roles and expectations.

The moderate accessibility ratings from both groups indicated that although Iriga City PESO services are generally reachable, access is not yet optimal. This points to structural or contextual barriers, including communication channels, geographical location, or digital limitations, that prevent certain clients from fully benefiting from available services.

The substantial outcomes achieved ratings implied that once clients are able to access the service of Iriga City PESO, the office is generally successful in delivering results, particularly in facilitating employment opportunities and supporting workforce development.

The high satisfaction levels reported by both jobseekers and enterprise employers suggested that clients value the quality of interaction, staff professionalism, and overall support provided by Iriga City PESO. This reflected strong frontline service delivery and reinforces the office's credibility among its stakeholders.

The perception of established efficiency indicated that Iriga City PESO's internal processes and workflows are dependable and well managed, allowing services to be delivered in a timely and organized manner.

Overall, the data suggest that Iriga City PESO delivers dependable and effective employment services that generate meaningful outcomes, satisfy both jobseekers and employers, and operate with demonstrable efficiency. However, the recurring "moderately accessible" rating from both groups indicates an opportunity to further improve outreach, communication, and ease of service access to optimize user experience and widen impact.

Conclusion B

Research Objective 2: Compare the Jobseekers and Enterprise Employers' perceived effectiveness of the Performance Management of Iriga City PESO's employment services in terms Accessibility, Outcomes Achieved, Satisfaction with Services, and Efficiency of Service.

The results of the study reveal that there are no significant difference between the jobseekers' and enterprise employer's perceptions of effectiveness of Iriga City PESO's delivery of services across the four key dimensions of performance management.

This statistically unified perceptions implied that Iriga City PESO delivers their services in a consistent and balanced way, regardless of client type. As an mediator between jobseekers and enterprise employers, the office appeared to have uniform processes, standardized service delivery, and comparable outcomes, leading both groups to form matched assessments of the four dimensions. Such consistency is a positive indicator of institutional reliability and fairness in providing services.

More importantly, the absence of significant differences does not suggest mediocrity, but rather reflects a shared experience of Iriga City PESO's strengths and limitations. Both groups similarly recognize areas where the office performs well, such as achieving outcomes and maintaining efficient operations, as well as areas that require further enhancement, particularly in accessibility and operational adjustments.

Overall, these findings underscore that Iriga City PESO functions as a stable and dependable employment service provides, and that future improvements should focus on system-wide enhancements rather than client-specific adjustments to further elevate its overall performance.

Conclusion C

Research Objective 3: Propose a Sustainable Framework for Action (SFA) based on the ILO's Performance Management element incorporating the feedback from the Jobseekers and Enterprise Employers.

Input

The input for this study includes the PPAs of the Iriga City PESO for the calendar year 2024 from the office's annual accomplishment report. This served as the baseline data regarding the performance of the Iriga City PESO. The other input for this study is the perceived effectiveness of the jobseekers and enterprise employers regarding the four dimensions: Accessibility, Outcomes Achieved, Satisfaction with Services, and Efficiency of Service, under the Performance Management Element of the delivery framework of ILO. This provides both quantitative and qualitative data, serving as a guide in drafting the SFA that is proposed to Iriga City PESO.

Process

The process for this study starts with analyzing the data from the annual accomplishment report of Iriga City PESO for the calendar year 2024 through the lens of the delivery framework of ILO. It is followed by the analysis of the data gathered from the perceived effectiveness of the jobseekers and enterprise employers of the four dimensions under the performance management element of the delivery framework of ILO. This was done by getting the mean of the data and identifying whether there is a significant difference between the perceived effectiveness of the services of Iriga City PESO by the jobseekers and the enterprise employers via independent sample t-test. The responses gathered from the interview was analyzed thematically. Lastly, the proposed SFA was drafted considering the analyzed data gathered from the samples.

Output

The output of this study is the proposed Sustainable Framework for Action for improving the performance management of Iriga City PESO.

The Sustainable Framework for Action (SFA) is structured based on the Performance Measurement Framework (PMF) of the performance management element of the delivery framework by ILO.

The inputs of the framework are Database System, Human Capital Training, and Operational Resources. Basically these are the resources needed in order to achieve the impact of the framework.

The outputs are Operational Efficiency, Matching Quality, and Extensive Programming. These are the short-term activities or programs that Iriga City PESO need to conduct in order for them to produce the outcomes.

The outcomes in the framework are Candidate Tracking, Employability Enhancement, and Inclusivity and Access. These are the medium-term results of the outputs that directly affect the desired impact.

Finally, the main impact of this framework is sustainable employment which is characterized by maintained employment rates, high work retention, and low turnover rates.

VIII.RECOMMENDATIONS

Recommendation A

The results have shown that at its current state, Iriga City PESO has a high level of effectiveness and efficiency. Interviews with their customers who had first-hand encounters with them revealed niche-level gaps and limitations in the office's workflow.

The following are short-term recommendations that are the most feasible for the office. First is to institutionalize multi-platform communication systems. Iriga City PESO can immediately improve accessibility by standardizing the use of multiple communication channels aside from their Facebook page. They may use email, text messages, and/or on-site postings. Establishing clear response time protocols and communication guidelines can quickly reduce accessibility gaps. Second is to continue or improve staff capacity building. They should conduct regular staff trainings focused on customer service, responsiveness, and most especially, digital communication. These can be implemented using existing resources and will reinforce professionalism and consistency in dealing with customers. Third, is to develop contingency plans to improve peak-season responsiveness. Contingency measures during these

periods may include temporary task reallocation, pre-scheduling employer requests, and the like can be done to prevent congestion without major structural changes.

The following long-term recommendations require more time and resources but, if executed right, should greatly improve their effectiveness. First is to strengthen employer engagement and feedback mechanisms. By establishing regular employer consultations, feedback surveys, and labor market conversations, the office would help align their services with industry needs. Over time, this should improve referral quality and reduce the disconnect that jobseekers and enterprise employers experienced. Second is to invest in technology and data-driven systems. Alongside the first long-term recommendation, the development and institutionalization of a modern, data-driven job matching and labor market information system should be treated as a strategic investment. This requires sustained funding, policy integration, continuous system upgrading, which are costly and time-consuming, but doing so would ultimately strengthen their effectiveness.

Recommendation B

Along the lines of the recommendations from the first research objective, given that the jobseekers and enterprise employers share similar perceptions of Iriga City PESO's service effectiveness in terms of the four dimensions of the performance management, they may enforce several actions to further enhance their service delivery.

To keep it concise, they must sustain and enhance current service standards by implementing feedback-driven improvements (Database System), expand stakeholder collaboration (Human Capital Training), invest in staff training (Operational Resources), and overall procedural and technological upgrades (Matching Quality, Extensive Programming, and Candidate Tracking).

By implementing these recommendations, Iriga City PESO can continue to strengthen its delivery of services, satisfying the ever changing needs of jobseekers and enterprise employers, and performing their core duties and functions. This would require future researches that focuses on longitudinal or comparative PESO studies.

Recommendation C

The implementation of the Sustainable Framework for Action (SFA) for Iriga City PESO would result to significant implications for the following sectors: LGU Iriga, DOLE/PESO Network, and TESDA.

For the LGU Iriga, they may adopt a formal ordinance integrating the SFA for Iriga City PESO into local and labor employment programs. This ensures continuity, accountability, and strategic alignment with the city's development plans. They may also consider increasing or securing dedicated funds to support improved Iriga City PESO's operations. Lastly, they may create policies requiring regular assessment of the services and other outputs of the office based on the SFA. This enhances transparency and encourages evidence-based decision-making.

For the DOLE/PESO Network, they may adopt the SFA, allowing the DOLE to develop national guidelines that unify assessment metrics on accessibility, outcomes, satisfaction, and efficiency across all PESOs in the province, or if possible, in the country. They may also issue policies institutionalizing mandatory training for PESO staff on labor market information, digital tools, case management, and customer service. They can also create policies including annual performance audits and cross-PESO benchmarking to recognize best practices vis-a-vis to identify areas needing intervention.

For TESDA, they may institutionalize policies requiring training regulations based on the data gathered by PESO. They can also develop policies that require routine coordination with local PESOs for student profiling, training needs assessments, and job placement services. They may also strengthen policies mandating soft skills training, career coaching, and job-readiness programs directly linked to PESO services. Lastly, they can establish shared monitoring systems with PESO to track employment outcomes, ensuring accountability and program relevance.

Aside from those sectors, future research agenda may also be conducted in relation to the impact of institutionalizing the proposed framework. The database in the SFA may be benchmarked and validated by related offices, including Department of Labor and Employment, and Department of Trade and Industry. Future research may also focus on allocating or assignment of roles to specific Iriga City PESO personnel to guarantee effective institutionalization. Other basis for framework may also be looked into such as the Republic Act No. 11032. Other focus may include, but not limited to, longitudinal tracing of beneficiaries, comparative studies with other cities, and digital PESO transformation.

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